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D2.3: Social Lab Implementation Report 2: strategies for responding to environment and climate ethical issues in the context of R&I and for the green transition

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9.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	European network
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12.	Partner	University of Cape Town	UCT	South Africa
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Executive Summary

This document provides the second report on the implementation activities of the RE4GREEN Social Labs, covering the period from May 2025 to December 2025. The RE4GREEN project, “Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition,” focuses on supporting the European Commission to better integrate climate and environmental research ethics and research integrity considerations into its research and innovation (R&I) programming. The Social Lab process was launched in April 2024 to bring together people from across sectors and R&I domains across the European Research Area, as well as from South Africa and Japan. These Social Labs create participatory spaces for exploring and addressing issues of environmental and climate ethics in the context of R&I in general and for the Green Transition.

As reported in Deliverable 2.2 (Csábi et al., 2025), the first phase of Social Lab work...

...engaged in familiarization with Horizon Europe’s research and innovation funding structures, aligning their thematic areas with six Horizon Europe clusters, five missions, and several partnerships. This foundational work ensured that the Social Labs were well-integrated with the European Research Area (ERA) and focused on six thematic areas of Horizon Europe clusters. International perspectives from Japan and South Africa broadened the scope to global considerations of environmental and climate ethics.

Key activities during this phase included the recruitment of Social Lab participants by conducting more than 120 interviews with stakeholders across sectors, the design and facilitation of two participatory workshops across eight Social Labs. The findings from these activities revealed a range of significant issues. The interviews and first set of workshops highlighted cross-cutting concerns about resource use and intensity, the environmental impact of R&I practices, technoeconomic challenges, and justice and equity considerations amongst others. These first workshops revealed shared recognition of the tensions between driving technological and scientific innovation and minimizing environmental harm.

The second set of workshops delved deeper into the relationship between the issues identified and the goals of the European Green Transition. Participants engaged in reflective exercises discussing how their work in R&I advances and hinders the green transition. Participants also explored potential actions to address environmental and climate ethics issues from workshop 1. The second workshop highlighted the need for cross-sectoral collaboration, inclusive governance, and clearly defined responsibilities at all levels – from individual researchers to international policy frameworks. These workshop findings underscored the need for systemic reforms in governance, funding, and institutional priorities, as well as for fostering epistemic justice and broad participation to ensure diverse perspectives are integrated into decisions about the green transition.

In this second phase of Social Lab reporting in RE4GREEN, we share results from workshops three and four and about the international labs. In workshop 3, participants met online and reviewed the results of: an initial policy brief from RE4GREEN to address climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues in EU R&I; and a set of competences intended to support stakeholders, funders, and researchers across the EU R&I system to consider these

climate and environmental ethics issues and responses. In workshop 4, participants met in person and engaged in a range of activities to grapple with the EU “Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle”; online training materials in development by RE4GREEN; and envision futures of the EU R&I system where significant harms are tended to in different ways.

The findings from workshops three and four and from the international Social Labs underline that environmental and climate ethics in R&I cannot be addressed at the project level alone. Participants highly supported the direction of RE4GREEN’s policy recommendations, competency framework, and training approach, while emphasising the need for stronger institutional responsibility and better alignment with existing governance and funding processes. The discussions around the DNSH principle showed that it helps orient reflection on environmental harms but is difficult to apply due to broad definitions of objectives, unclear thresholds for “significant”, and uncertainties around responsibility for systemic impacts. Across the labs, participants pointed to fragmented policies, weak enforcement, and a gap between formal responsibility and practical action. Insights from the Social Labs in Japan and South Africa reinforced these findings by highlighting how local contexts, governance structures, and historically engrained power relations shape both the experience of environmental harms and the possibilities for responsibility and change. Overall, the findings highlight the need for a more coherent, coordinated approach to address issues of environmental and climate ethics in research and for environmental sustainability to be a guiding value within this ecosystem, supported by clearer accountability and action across actors and levels.

1 Scoping: Social Lab Implementation Report 2

Deliverable 2.3 is a second report on the implementation activities of the RE4GREEN Social Labs. The Social Lab process was launched in April 2024; the first Social Lab report delivered in May 2025. After the release of this second implementation report (December 2025) the Deliverable 2.1 Social Lab Methodology will be released in January 2027. This second implementation report focuses on participant’s experiences with Social Lab workshops three and four. In this phase, participants explored various ways of responding to climate and environmental ethics issues in EU R&I prepared by the RE4GREEN project, and grappled with questions of how to apply the Do No Significant Harm Principle in EU R&I.

Work in this phase of the RE4GREEN Social Lab process included a series of 3,5-hour online workshops (workshop 3, hosted by individual Social Labs) and a series of 1.5-day in-person workshops (workshop 4, hosted by individual Social Labs in their corresponding countries). Results of workshop 3 are presented in section 2 results of workshop 4 are presented in section 3. In addition, a set of contextually customized workshops took place with participants in the Japan and South Africa Social Labs, convened by researchers at the Universities of Tokyo and University of Cape Town, respectively (see section 4). A closing discussion weaves together findings from the whole Social Lab process of RE4GREEN (section 5).

1.1 Re-Introducing the Social Labs

The RE4GREEN Social Lab portfolio maps to European Commission R&I framework funding structures, in response to the initial funding call requirements to focus on the European Research Area (Figure 1).

* The European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) is not part of the Specific Programme

Figure 1: Horizon Europe Framework Program Structure. The RE4GREEN Social Labs focus on Pillar II funding, as well as the Missions and Partnerships, not shown.

Beyond the European Research Area, the RE4GREEN Social Labs also include two International Companion Labs – one based in South Africa, at the University of Cape Town, and one based in Japan, at the University of Tokyo. The Social Labs also benefit from a general supporting partner based in the Republic of Korea at Korea University. The inclusion of International Companion Labs helps to reveal wider perspectives on climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues – issues which themselves are often global in character.

Figure 2: Visualisation of RE4GREEN Social Labs and integration of the Social Lab work package (WP2) in the context of other project activities.

Each Social Lab is led by a different RE4GREEN project partner (

Institution	Lab no.	Lab focus
EARMA	1	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 7)
AIT	2	Digital, industry and space
ECSA	3	Climate and mobility
AU	4	Energy
UAB	5	Fresh waters and oceans
UBO	6	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 8)
UTokyo	7	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 1)
UCT	8	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 6)

Table 1).

Institution	Lab no.	Lab focus
EARMA	1	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 7)
AIT	2	Digital, industry and space
ECSA	3	Climate and mobility
AU	4	Energy
UAB	5	Fresh waters and oceans
UBO	6	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 8)
UTokyo	7	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 1)
UCT	8	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 6)

Table 1: Social Lab assignments within the RE4GREEN project.

The first phase of implementation involved Social Lab leaders based at each RE4GREEN partner organization familiarizing themselves with the scope of each Horizon Europe and broader ERA R&I funding area.

1.2 Summary of themes covered by the Social Labs

Social Lab 1: Health, Culture, and Inclusive Society; Civil Security

The first Social Lab focuses on four interconnected themes: health, culture, inclusive society, and civil security. The health component encompasses a broad spectrum of research areas aimed at improving healthcare systems, addressing health disparities, and advancing medical breakthroughs. The culture and inclusive society theme seek to foster social cohesion by addressing inequalities and promoting diversity. Research under this theme explores cultural heritage preservation, cultural exchange, and the empowerment of marginalized communities. It also delves into education, employment opportunities, and social integration strategies to create equitable societies that embrace inclusivity. The civil security for society component focuses on ensuring the safety and resilience of communities against various threats such as crime, terrorism, natural disasters, and cybersecurity breaches.

Social Lab 2: Digital, Industry and Space

This lab's theme builds upon Horizon Europe's Cluster 4: Digital, Industry, and Space. This cluster's overarching vision is to create competitive technologies that respect planetary limits while driving innovation in the digital sector, space technologies and industry. The research areas emphasize digital transformation, including artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, quantum computing, next-generation internet technologies, and advanced materials. These innovations aim to enhance industrial competitiveness while supporting sustainable practices. In the space sector, this cluster covers research on Earth observation technologies such as Copernicus services for climate monitoring and disaster management. It also explores innovative space applications for navigation, communication, and environmental research. The research topics in this lab include industry-specific challenges, such as transitioning to climate-neutral production systems through circular economy, and low-carbon technologies, sustainable materials production and resource efficiency.

Social Lab 3: Climate and Mobility

The theme of Social Lab 3 builds upon Horizon Europe's Cluster 5: Climate, Energy, and Mobility while focusing strictly on climate and mobility. The main aim behind Cluster 5's research and innovation activities on climate and mobility is to fight climate change by better understanding its causes, evolution, risks, impacts and opportunities, specifically by making the transport sectors more climate and environment-friendly, more efficient and competitive, smarter, safer and more resilient.

Social Lab 4: Energy

This lab covers research areas that aim to transform energy systems into sustainable models that align with climate neutrality goals. Research focuses on renewable energy technologies like solar power while exploring efficient energy storage solutions such as batteries and carbon capture utilization/storage (CCUS) methods to mitigate emissions from industrial processes. Efforts in this research area are directed towards improving energy efficiency in buildings through smart technologies that reduce emissions. Citizen engagement, as a research method, plays a pivotal role in fostering public support for energy transitions.

Social Lab 5: Fresh Waters and Oceans

This lab covers research areas that work on critical challenges related to water conservation and ocean sustainability. Key themes include developing desalination plants for freshwater supply while mitigating environmental impacts such as brine discharge. Wastewater treatment innovations aim to reduce pollution while ensuring water quality standards are met. Ocean-related research explores sustainable fishing practices that minimize bycatch alongside aquaculture methods that reduce ecological footprints. Technologies like tidal energy plants are investigated for their potential in renewable energy generation while balancing ecosystem

impacts. The lab also covers research areas that examines water-intensive activities like mining by promoting recycling technologies that reduce freshwater demand and pollution risks.

Social Lab 6: Food Systems; Bioeconomy; Agriculture; Environment; Soil; Natural resources

Social Lab 6 explores research areas of Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment). This cluster aims at reducing environmental degradation, halting and reversing the decline of biodiversity, and better managing natural resources through transformative changes of the economy and society in both urban and rural areas. It intends to ensure food and nutrition security for all within planetary boundaries through knowledge, innovation and digitalisation in agriculture and food systems, and steer and accelerate the transition to a low carbon, resource efficient circular economy and sustainable bioeconomy, including forestry.

Social Lab 7 (Japan): Health, Culture, and Inclusive Society; Civil Security

Sharing the Social Lab 1 themes of health, culture, inclusive society, and civil security, Social Lab 7 (UTokyo) covers environmental ethics, post-disaster reconstruction, community resilience, and rural revitalization. It focuses on the social aspects of technological innovation, the ethical challenges of sustainability, and the intersection of human and non-human worlds. Some of the key thematic areas discussed were environmental justice and equity in decision-making, cultural construction of place and memory, and redefining nature in Japanese social and philosophical contexts.

Social Lab 8 (South Africa): Food Systems; Bioeconomy; Agriculture; Environment (as SL6)

Operating in South Africa, this lab covers research and development areas tailored to local contexts within Horizon Europe's Clusters 5 (Climate) & 6 (Food Systems). In the second phase of the Social Lab process the UCT team narrowed its focus to Agrifood systems. The decision to focus on agrifood systems alone, instead of the four divergent themes explored in the first implementation phase was made because it became exceedingly difficult to recruit participants from the four themes (lab-grown meat, digital agriculture, payments for biodiversity conservation, and the bioeconomy) into the next workshops. The change to the topic is explained in more detail in section 1.3 below.

2 Social Lab Workshop 3

Social Lab Workshop 3 aimed at exploring participants responses to policy recommendations developed by the RE4GREEN project to advance consideration of climate and environmental research ethics and integrity issues in EU R&I. In addition, WS3 also focused on a review of various competences constructed by RE4GREEN to support people across EU R&I systems to recognize and respond to climate and environmental ethics issues. In response to participant feedback on the challenge of long-duration online sessions, workshops were compressed to take place over 2-hours, with about 1-hour of preparatory work shared with participants to avoid reduction of effective time together. We used the online digital whiteboard "[Mural](#)" for collaborative and interactive work. The workshops were conducted from May 2025 to mid-September 2025 across the Social Labs. Informed consent for participation in Workshop 3 followed from the original consent process reported in Phase 1, deliverable 2.2 (Csabi et al., 2025).¹

2.1 Aims and scope

Workshop 3 was designed by the AIT team and began with a welcome round for new participants and an introductory recapitulation of results from previous workshop. A first session then unfolded over 45 minutes in which participants provided feedback on guidelines and policy recommendations. Participants were first asked to use a sliding scale on Mural to convey their perspective on the clarity of the guidelines. Second, participants were asked to assess the relevance of the guidelines to their particular fields of work. The first session was concluded by an open discussion on particular aspects of the guidelines found to be important; missing; or needing tailoring for their fields of work.

After a brief break, participants then spent 45 minutes in a reflection on the competences crafted by the RE4GREEN project as being needed to identify and respond to climate and environmental ethics issues in green-transition-related R&I. In this second session, participants reviewed competences individually and assessed those competences deemed relevant to their fields of work. Participants were then asked to share individual case examples of where specific competences may have been applied and / or might have been needed. Finally, participants engaged in a plenary discussion of under what circumstances they might have need or seek trainings to build such competences. A final plenary closed the workshop with questions regarding participant interest in having any of the materials shared for their organizations, as well as opinions on carrying activity forward after the conclusion of the fourth Social Lab workshop.

¹ All workshops were conducted with informed consent of participants in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), using a consent form (Annex 4 – Workshop Consent Form) reviewed and approved by the German Reference Centre for Ethics in the Life Sciences. The Research Ethics Committee at UAB requested minor modifications to the Consent Form in accordance with current participatory research standards, resulting in the necessary ethics approval. The same was the case for AU who applied for ethics approval for SL4 at Aarhus University for the study RE4GREEN, Social Lab on Energy, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University, approval no. BSS-2024-098-L.

2.1.1 Reviewing policy recommendations

In the first part of workshop 3 participants were asked to review an excerpt of the draft Policy Brief. The brief was developed by WP3 through an iterative, evidence-based process that combined systematic analysis of existing research ethics and integrity frameworks, expert review, and validation through conferences, workshops, and advisory board feedback, as well as this SL activity. The policy recommendations identified gaps in current research governance and gives concrete, actionable guidance that helps institutions embed environmental and climate ethics into research practice, strengthening accountability, justice, and sustainability in the green transition. Due to the limited time there was for the workshop, it was not practical to ask participants to read and comment on the full Policy Brief. We therefore focused on the recommended stakeholder actions section as a central part of the brief and directly linked to the roles and responsibilities of different actors within the research system.

Presenting only the stakeholder actions allowed participants to engage with a manageable amount of material and to comment on how the recommendations relate to their own professional contexts. Despite reviewing only one section of the brief, the feedback received touched on broader issues of scope, feasibility, and responsibility, and contributed to revisions both within the Policy Brief and in the wider orientation of the work in WP3.

Participants were presented with a Mural board where the stakeholder actions were rated by understandability and relevance on a sliding scale as seen on Figure 3.

Figure 3: Excerpt of a Mural board of WS3 with the sliding-scale exercise for ranking stakeholder actions' relevance

2.1.2 Reviewing competences

In the second part of workshop 3 participants were provided with a Mural board (Figure 4) displaying the Competence Profile developed by WP4 and were asked to indicate their assessment on the interactive board. This approach enabled participants to quickly express judgments on the relevance of competences while also allowing patterns of agreement and disagreement to emerge across Social Labs.

The RE4GREEN Competence Profile developed by WP4 is based on extensive interviews and surveys with environmental education and research integrity specialists. Its structure emulates the EU GreenComp framework, which defines sustainability as “prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries” (Bianchi et al 2022). Competence profiles can help ensure all actors have the skills, knowledge, attitudes and abilities to contribute to the green transition. It is used as a basis for designing ‘micromodules’ that can be combined into tailored training pathways for students, researchers, ethics reviewers, and citizen scientists.

Figure 4: Excerpt of a Mural board of WS3 with the up and down arrows exercise to provide feedback on the relevance on Competence Profiles

The full Competence Profile can be found in Annex 1.

2.2 Participation in Workshop 3

Following the interviews, the SL participants were invited to join the workshops. To expand the coverage of the participation, we recruited additional participants. In total, we had 41 participants across the SLs. The gender distribution of participants was 22 females, 18 males, and 1 non-binary individual.

Participation by sectors were research performing (59%), civil society and media (7%), public sector including funders and research ethics committees (5%), private sector (22%), and other (7%) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Workshop 3 participation by sector.

Figure 6: Geographical distribution of WS3 participants. Austria:2, France: 1, Latvia: 2, Portugal: 3, Spain: 7, Switzerland: 1, Belgium: 1, Czech Republic: 1, Germany: 8, Luxemburg: 1, Greece: 1, Italy: 1, Netherlands: 2, Finland: 1, Norway: 1, UK: 3, Denmark: 1, Hungary:1, Chile: 1, USA: 2, South Korea: 1 (If the participants have double affiliations or their organisations have multiple locations, we counted all of them.)

The geographic locations of the participants' organisations covered most of Central, Western, Northern, and Southern Europe. Additionally, we invited participants from other countries including South Korea, USA and Chile (Figure 6).

2.3 Results

The results of WS3 contributed closely to the work done in WP3 and WP4. Participants evaluated the relevance and clarity of various recommended actions on the policy level to support the integration of environmental and climate ethics into R&I. The results also deepened our understanding of participants sense of competences needed to understand and address climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues in R&I practices.

2.3.1 Participants' perspectives on policy recommendations

Sliding-scale results - relevance

Table 1 Participants generally rated the stakeholder action areas as relevant, with most categories receiving average scores around 3 on the 1–4 relevance scale. Strategic vision and institutional policy and research conduct and mentoring received the highest mean scores (both 3.2), indicating that these areas were considered the most relevant among the options presented. Implementation and compliance, teaching and training design, and curriculum oversight and research priorities also scored within a similar range, with means between 3.0 and 3.1. Ethics review and oversight received the lowest relevance rating, with a mean of 2.6 and a median of 2.5. Overall, the results show that participants considered all areas at least moderately relevant, with some categories viewed as more central than others based on their higher average and median scores. A detailed presentation of the mean, median and modal response values are presented in Table 2. The sliding scale results only presents five Social Labs, as SL6 (*food, bioeconomy & agriculture*) had to split their workshop into three online meetings due to scheduling conflicts with participants. Given the limited time of these meetings, they spent the time discussing the policy recommendations hence their input is integrated into the next section called "Discussion questions results".

4 = highly relevant

3 = relevant

2 = only a little relevant

1 = not relevant

You can also give half a points.]

Example: You can see the mark is at 4 on this picture above.

Figure 7: Explanation of slide-scale scoring

Table 2: Participant ranking of relevance of different policy recommendations.

	Total relevance score	Number of responses	Mean response value	Median response value	Modal response value
Strategic vision and institutional policy	89.5	28	3.2	3.5	3.5
Ethics review and oversight	75.5	29	2.6	2.5	2.5
Curriculum oversight and research priorities	82.5	28	2.9	3	4
Implementation and compliance	85.5	28	3.1	3	3
Teaching and training design	84.5	28	3.0	3	3.5
Research conduct and mentoring	87	27	3.2	3.5	3

Sliding-scale results - understandability

Participants ranked the stakeholder actions on a sliding scale between easy to understand (score: 1) and hard to understand (score: 5) as seen on Figure 8. Table 3 Participants generally found all stakeholder action areas easy to understand. Mean scores across categories ranged from 1.8 to 2.5 on the 1–5 scale, indicating that most responses fell between “easy to understand” and “understandable.” The categories teaching and training design, implementation and compliance, and research conduct and mentoring received the lowest mean scores (1.8–1.9), suggesting they were the easiest for participants to interpret. Strategic vision and institutional policy had the highest mean score (2.5), making it the least easy category, though its median and mode (both 2) show that most participants still rated it as closer to “easy to understand” than to “hard to understand.” Overall, all categories were viewed as clearly understandable. A detailed presentation of the mean, median and modal response values are presented in Table 3.

1-----2-----3-----4-----5

1 = easy to understand

2 = in between easy to understand and understandable

3 = understandable

4 = in between understandable and hard to understand

5 = hard to understand

Example: You can see the mark is at 2 on this picture above.

Figure 8: Example slide-scale on Mural for participants to convey perceptions of clarity of the stakeholder actions

	Total understandability score	Number of responses	Mean response value	Median response value	Modal response value
Strategic vision and institutional policy	72	29	2.5	2	2
Ethics review and oversight	71	29	2.4	2	2
Curriculum oversight and research priorities	56	28	2.0	2	1
Implementation and compliance	52	28	1.9	2	1
Teaching and training design	51	28	1.8	2	1
Research conduct and mentoring	53	28	1.9	2	1

Table 3: Participant ranking of relevance of different policy recommendations

Discussion Questions Results

SL1 (health, culture & civil security)

In SL1 when asked about what might be missing or what could be improved, participants commented in some places on the format of the brief. More generally, they said it would be helpful to have supporting material on ethics self-assessment, but to do so without overloading all parties involved (e.g., researchers and review committee members). In addition, they noted that it would be useful to connect guidelines to existing EU regulation and implementation efforts, and to provide more concrete outcome measures connected to said guidelines.

SL2 (digital, industry and space)

SL2 discussions focused on field-specificity. Participants noted that environmental ethics looks different in chemistry, electrical engineering, and other disciplines, and therefore requires field-adapted content, criteria, warning signs, and case studies. They highlighted the role of supervisors and managers in shaping research culture and transferring ethical practices. They also pointed to the need for sustainability visions and examples relevant in local contexts. Although the actions were seen as clear, participants were unsure how to implement them without practical examples, quantified criteria, and context-specific training.

SL3 (climate and mobility)

In SL3, participants stressed the need to build environmental ethics into education and to be clearer about what responsibilities sit with institutional leadership. They recommended refining distinctions within the strategic vision section, adding issues such as public vs. private funding, digital infrastructure impacts, and broader building and procurement practices. They also noted gaps related to funding sources, data ethics, and the treatment of vulnerable populations. They also wanted additional guidance at both the institutional and field-specific levels, recommending a two-tier approach: broad EU-level guidelines complemented by more targeted, discipline-specific tools or recommendations.

SL4 (energy)

SL4 participants discussed the need for clearer roles and responsibilities, especially when it comes to different levels of leadership (e.g., university senior management vs. deans). They proposed integrating environmental reflection into research workflows through mechanisms like SWOT-style assessments, including for journal submissions or patent applications. They also discussed how the guidelines apply beyond academia, particularly in the private sector, and highlighted differences in time horizons between industry and academia. Incentive structures were also mentioned, alongside interest in open-access life-cycle analyses.

SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)

In SL5, participants highlighted missing perspectives related to feasibility, funders, policy makers, industry–research collaboration, and citizen science. Participants emphasized that funders should specify environmental requirements and that guidelines may need to be tailored for non-academic organizations, especially those engaged in citizen science. Participants also noted that the relevance of the guidelines varies by field. Some disciplines may require tailored versions, while others (such as anthropology) might not.

SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)

In SL6, participants raised practical concerns about communication, noting that while funders and policymakers are reachable, it is difficult to effectively reach ethics committees, researchers, and innovators at scale. They also highlighted feasibility challenges. Many recommendations lack measurable KPIs, making them difficult to operationalize within existing funding and evaluation systems. Participants also pointed out missing perspectives, including the diversity of national R&I contexts, the need to give biodiversity greater prominence alongside climate, and the importance of adding publishers, industry, and additional disciplines (economics, sociology) to the stakeholder landscape. They also added that discourse and participation require more attention. Regarding field relevance, participants noted that some disciplines (especially social sciences) struggle to see themselves in the stakeholder list. They warned that

broad guidelines can risk enabling greenwashing and emphasized the need to strengthen networking and knowledge-sharing across the R&I ecosystem.

Closing observations from SLs

Across the six Social Labs, participants expressed broad support for the direction and intent of the recommendations but also raised consistent concerns about feasibility and practical implementation. A recurring theme was the need to shift responsibility from individual researchers toward institutions, funders, publishers, and private-sector actors. Many Labs noted that without these additional stakeholders (particularly funding organisations and editorial boards) the recommendations cannot realistically be implemented or sustained. This was accompanied by a strong call to expand the scope beyond universities to include a wider range of Research Performing Organisations and industry partners.

Another common insight was that while the recommendations are clear at a conceptual level, they remain too general to be applied in practice. Participants across Labs independently requested discipline-specific examples, field-adapted criteria, context-sensitive case studies, and operational tools such as crosswalks to existing EU regulations. This pattern complements the scoring results: most categories were rated as easy to understand, yet strategic institutional policy, which was rated the most relevant, was also among the hardest to interpret, reflecting its perceived complexity and level of abstraction. In contrast, ethics review and oversight consistently the lowest relevance score and was widely viewed as overburdened, echoing concerns that ethics committees cannot absorb additional responsibilities.

Participants also highlighted several gaps, particularly the need to give biodiversity greater prominence, to better integrate social sciences and economics, and to account for differences across national R&I systems. Finally, concerns about feasibility were common. Researchers often lack incentives, measurable KPIs, time, or resources to implement new ethical practices. Overall, the combined feedback points to strong support for the recommendations' aims but also a shared expectation that they must be accompanied by more concrete guidance, broader stakeholder inclusion, and realistic pathways for implementation.

How Social Lab Feedback Informed the Policy Brief and the Direction of WP3

The SL discussions provided essential insights for the development of the policy brief, and many of their insights shaped the final version. While it was not possible to incorporate every suggestion into a single, concise document, several themes from the Labs directly informed the published recommendations². For example, participants asked for the scope to extend beyond universities to include a wider range of Research Performing Organisations and institutional actors. Participants also stressed the need to strengthen institutional responsibility rather than placing the burden on individual researchers; this is addressed throughout the brief, where all six recommendations are framed as institutional, structural actions rather than behavioural guidelines for individuals. Several SLs noted that high-level recommendations are valuable only when accompanied by concrete pathways for action. To respond to this, the policy brief intentionally anchors its recommendations in established and widely recognised tools and frameworks rather than creating new standalone instruments. For example, the brief explicitly links to the SDGs, the Paris Agreement, the European Green Deal, DNSH, Horizon Europe

² [Embedding Environmental and Climate Ethics in Research: Six Recommendations for Institutions](#)

obligations, the CARE Principles, and UNESCO's LINKS programme. Although the format of a short policy brief did not allow us to include fully developed tools, the SL feedback strongly influenced our decision to recommend their creation directly within the brief. Several sections explicitly call for the development of practical resources to support implementation.

Beyond the policy brief itself, the SL feedback played a significant role in shaping the strategic orientation of WP3 as a whole. Participants consistently emphasised that the sector does not need additional high-level frameworks but rather adaptations of existing processes, along with practical tools that help institutions translate environmental and climate ethics into everyday decision-making. In response, WP3 prioritises building on established structures (such as the ECoC, the forthcoming EU Guidance Note (European Commission, 2025) on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research, and existing RE&RI procedures) by integrating environmental and climate considerations into them rather than creating parallel systems. The SL also highlighted the need for concrete support for ethics committees, project teams, and researchers working with citizens. This led to the decision to develop targeted WP3 outputs, including a tool for Research Ethics Committees, a risk assessment tool under Task 3.3, and practical resources for citizen-engaged research. These tools directly address the Labs' concerns about feasibility, operationalisation, and the diversity of research contexts. The insights from the SLs will help the project move beyond high-level principles toward actionable guidance that reflects the realities described by participants.

2.3.2 Participant perspectives on competences

Up and down voting

In this exercise, participants were asked to rate the relevance of each competency from RE4GREEN's competency framework by placing an upward facing (indicating "relevant") or downward facing ("not relevant") arrow next to their description on the Mural Board. In the two charts below, are listed those competencies that achieved either the highest (above 11 up votes) or lowest (above 4 down votes) scoring across the Social Labs.

Participants rated "considering the reduction of environmental harm and the increase of environmental benefits as a professional responsibility in R&I" (1.1.3) as the most relevant competency. This confirms the necessity of supplementing established codes of conduct with environmental aspects and integrating them into research ethics and integrity training from an early stage in education. A large proportion of participants also agreed that the 'do no significant harm' and 'precautionary' principles should be applied in relation to R&I (1.1.4), which was ranked as the second most important competency to be developed. Jointly in third place are five competencies, including acknowledging "diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice" (1.1.1); supporting "equity and justice for present and future generations" (1.2.3); conducting "all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to social and environmental justice in the green transition" (1.2.4); recognising "potential trade-offs between competing priorities" (2.2.1); and respecting "local and traditional knowledge and methods to address sustainability in R&I" (3.3.2). Most of these competencies emphasise the multiplicity of interests and the complexity of addressing environmental issues, such as

concern for future generations and trade-offs, as well as the acknowledgement of diverse values, perspectives, and traditional knowledge. Competency 1.2.4 resonates strongly with 1.1.3, confirming the centrality of environmental aspects in all R&I activities.

The claim that researchers and innovators should 'plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry' (3.3.4) was the least popular among participants, possibly due to its impracticality and the restrictions it places on the innovation process. Some participants also considered the recognition of 'the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice' (1.2.1), the use of 'techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project' (3.1.3), and the respect for 'local and traditional knowledge and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation' (3.3.2) to be irrelevant.

In general, competency domain one, 'Embodying Sustainability Values', is considered crucial by most SL participants as it comprises seven of the top 13 competencies and occupies five of the top three spots in the ranking. The competencies in this domain emphasise the environmental impact and dependency of R&I and promote sustainability values and fairness as central to good scientific conduct. Subdomain 1.3, 'Promoting Nature', which focuses on non-anthropocentric environmental values, is less popular than subdomains 1.1 and 1.2. At the same time, domain one shares all top-down votes with domain three, 'Envisioning Sustainable Futures', with each domain being listed three times in Table 4. Domains two and four occupy the middle ground, each being represented twice among the top competencies and not appearing in the top-down votes. The most ambiguous competencies are 1.2.2 and 3.3.2, which appear in both the top up- and down-votes. Overall, the total number of upvotes exceeds the number of downvotes for almost all competencies, with 3.3.4 being the only one that received one more downvote than upvote.

The results presented for the competency exercise only include those from Social Labs one to five, as Social Lab six conducted three discussion-based online meetings, each with only some of the participants. However, the results from this lab contributed to the comment section below.

*Table 4: RE4GREEN competences with the highest number of up-votes across the Social Labs (cut-off 11 or above). *Indicates also top down-votes*

Number	Competence Item	Number of up votes
1.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... consider reducing environmental harms and increasing environmental benefits to be a professional responsibility in research and innovation.	20
1.1.4	Researchers and innovators should... apply the do no (significant) harm principle and precautionary principle in relation to research and innovation.	15
1.1.1	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice in the context of research and innovation.	14

1.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... support equity and justice for present and future generations in research and innovation proposals.	14
1.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... conduct all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice in the green transition.	14
2.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognize potential trade-offs between competing priorities (people, planet, profit) in research and innovation.	14
3.3.2*	Researchers and innovators should... respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.	14
1.2.2*	Researchers and innovators should... consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.	13
1.3.1	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.	13
2.1.1	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.	11
2.3.2	Researchers and innovators should... map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems.	11
4.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... be aware of the access to knowledge, networks and platforms that your role entails, and use this to promote environmentally and socially responsible action.	11
4.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... collaborate with multiple actors (such as policymakers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation.	11

Table 5: RE4GREEN competences with the highest number of down-votes across the Social Labs (cut-off 4 or above). **Indicates also top up-votes

Number	Competence Item	Number of down votes
3.3.4	Researchers and innovators should... plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design.)	7
1.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognize the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice.	5
3.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... employ techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project.	5

3.3.2**	Researchers and innovators should... respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.	5
1.2.2**	Researchers and innovators should... consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.	4
1.3.1	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.	4

Discussion Question Results

Can you think of an instance where one of these competences was applied?

Participants mentioned several instances in which they previously applied one or several of the competencies, including:

- Creating an explanatory video on the sustainability of research and publishing it on Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/reel/DF50ea3SQDg/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==).
- Giving a course on different stages of environmental impact
- helping with planning the construction of a supercomputer while considering environmental aspects in selecting its hardware and considering the future life cycle.
- Discussing the disposal of European E-Waste (Longterm thinking and multiple stakeholder engagement).
- Generally applying competencies of care and respect to the environment in ecology.
- Answering funding requirements to reduce harm.
- Identifying common challenges and uncertainties in a problem mapping for biosecurity.
- defining future scenarios and embracing complexity (system and critical thinking).
- Science communication in dialogue with policymakers.

While stakeholder engagement has a longer history in bioeconomy research in Cape Town, participants from Social Lab 8 emphasized the importance of related methodologies and suggested to make them more prominent in the competency profile.

Can you think of an instance where one of these competences would have been needed?

Potential uses of the competences across Social Lab participants included:

- Knowledge of systemic complexity to understand how research impacts can be either positive or negative.
- Understanding the agency of researchers and interactions with other stakeholder when it comes to climate action. This could strengthen the discursive abilities of researchers, when it comes to science-policy interactions.
- A broad understanding of coloniality is also relevant e.g. for working on carbon credit systems and defining relevant values/ deciding funding allocations between climate adaptation and mitigation.

- Understanding the significance of environmental and climate issues associated with research.
- Defining future scenarios and addressing conflicting goals or needs.
- Envisioning sustainable futures is unique to the RE4GREEN competency profile and could provide good input for biodiversity research.
- To learn more about community-based research methods could help bridging insecurities about methods and strategies.
- To navigate complex, large-scale and long-term problems, including tradeoffs such as energy efficiency during the research process vs. long-term effects from toxic materials.
- Awareness about coloniality were perceived to be helpful in cooperating with local stakeholders from the Global South.

SL8 acknowledged the value of the competencies as such but emphasized a more active approach that goes beyond recognizing the significance of climate issues and helps to understand how specific research can perpetuate systems of injustice.

What would you need to build these competences?

Resources mentioned to build competences:

- Training materials; also: for non-research related topics such as political actions (e.g. writing policy briefs).
- Interconnection and collaborations with research groups from other disciplines.
- Space for debate.
- Room to share experiences: Which decisions proved to be successful?
- Practical experience.
- Support tools
- More information.
- Time / money or other resources to implement them.

An alternative suggestion from *SL4 (energy)* was to think of competencies not to be possessed by an individual but rather to be covered by the research team as a whole. Research resources should be kept general, so they can be used by multiple disciplines. In SL8 it was emphasized that training needs to be co-developed with multiple stakeholders including communities who have been on the receiving end of unjust research systems. Researchers need to understand the gravity of the consequences of research in perpetuating systems of injustice. Participants in SL8 felt that training should involve an introduction to the political economy/ecology and history of research and how this has had a deeply extractive past, and if not handled with care can inadvertently perpetuate systems of power.

Would you seek trainings on these competences?

The willingness to participate in trainings was generally positive, however several conditions were mentioned:

- Relevance of tools / topics for specific research area or position of the person

- Qualification of the trainer, i.e. experience in specific disciplines, understanding of practical challenges
- Relevance of organizations offering the training
- Applicability: Trainings are not considered to be useful, if they are on a very abstract level.
- Time requirements should align with generally full schedules of researchers
- Trainings should be integrated into existing courses
- It should be advantageous to do the trainings, e.g. while applying for funds
- For SL8: See the remarks mentioned above.

What might make participating in such trainings attractive?

Attractivity of trainings materials could be enhanced by:

- Providing real life examples of best and poor practices; case studies with interactive learning.
- Providing clear elements that can be applied in practice.
- Making learning generally practical and close to application in general.
- Integration into existing courses.
- Making them accessible online and as in-person courses.
- Making them mandatory.
- Hosting them at community events, e.g. during conferences.
- Contextualizing contents of training materials socially and historically.
- Making them holistic.
- Providing a practical tool kit that can be taken away and used continuously.
- Providing a certificate or other incentives like a “sustainable research award”; training should increase the chances of receiving a grant.
- Being supported by the institution.
- Making additional use of training events e.g. for networking.
- Including more topics about North-South justice and equity and FAIR data practices.

Closing observations from all SLs

Across the Social Labs, there is strong convergence that the RE4GREEN competence framework is both relevant and necessary, especially in framing environmental responsibility, harm reduction, and justice as core elements of R&I. Competencies related to treating the reduction of environmental harm as a professional responsibility and applying the precautionary and DNSH principles were consistently rated as most important, confirming a shared view that environmental and climate considerations should be integrated into research ethics and integrity from an early stage. Domain 1, Embodying Sustainability Values, clearly dominates the highest-ranked competencies, highlighting broad agreement that sustainability, fairness, and concern for future generations are central to good scientific conduct. Competencies linked to long-term thinking and sustainable futures were also valued, indicating recognition of the need to address complexity, trade-offs, and diverse perspectives in the green transition.

At the same time, the results reveal tensions between ethical ambition and practical feasibility. Competencies that require comprehensive, continuous planning around sustainability throughout the entire research process were viewed more critically, often due to institutional constraints, limited time, and uncertainty about how such responsibilities can be operationalized. Mixed assessments of competencies related to futures thinking, coloniality, and local or traditional knowledge point to differences in disciplinary relevance and methodological confidence rather than outright rejection. Across the labs, participants emphasized that competence development requires practical, context-sensitive training, institutional support, and clear incentives, and that many competencies should be understood as collective capacities of research teams rather than individual skills. Overall, the findings suggest broad endorsement of the framework's direction, coupled with a clear call for actionable, supported, and socially grounded pathways for implementation.

2.4 Discussion of Workshop 3 Results

Across the six SLs, participants broadly supported the direction of the recommendations and offered insights that helped clarify where additional guidance or institutional support would be most valuable. While not all their recommendations could be implemented in a short brief, their emphasis on widening the scope beyond universities, strengthening institutional responsibility, and providing practical examples directly shaped the final policy brief, which now anchors its recommendations in established frameworks and calls for the development of concrete tools to support implementation. The labs also shaped WP3's broader orientation. Rather than creating new high-level frameworks, WP3 focuses on adapting existing processes (such as the ECoC, the forthcoming EU guidance note, and current RE&RI procedures) to integrate environmental and climate considerations in ways that reflect real research contexts. Their feedback also guided WP3 to prioritise targeted resources for RECs, project teams, and citizen-engaged research. In this way, the SLs provided a strong foundation for shaping both the brief and WP3's next steps.

All Social Lab participants considered RE4GREEN's competency framework to be generally relevant. Feedback from the labs helped set priorities when developing training pathways and micromodules in WP4 and provided valuable insights for their design and focus. Embodying sustainability values and emphasising the environmental impact of all R&I activities confirms the central objectives of RE4GREEN and helps to specify the training requirements of the broader research community. Discussions following the assessment helped clarify the various contexts in which competencies can be developed and applied, ranging from general interest in the subject to specific application cases. Training needs were not solely content-focused but also included structural requirements such as time and financial resources, interdisciplinary collaboration, and space for debate during training sessions, which will be of particular interest when it comes to implementation. Trainings were found to be most attractive when they were highly specific and practical. They should provide real-life examples of best practice and guidance for practitioners. Various labs suggested the possibility of a certification system to make participation more attractive.

3 Social Lab Workshop 4

Social Lab Workshop 4 aimed at engaging participants in reflections and critical discussion with the subject of the EU Do No Significant Harm Principle. Participants in this workshop were also introduced to and asked to provide feedback on the RE4GREEN set of training micromodules. Workshop 4 was the final planned gathering of each Social Lab. Each workshop was planned to take place over 1.5 days, in person, in host partner countries across Europe. Social Lab leaders each received a common agenda and set of participant workshops to support interactions and data collection. The workshops were conducted between mid-September 2025 and November 2025. Informed consent for participation in Workshop 4 followed from the original consent process reported in Phase 1, deliverable 2.2 (Csabi et al., 2025).³

3.1 Aims and scope

The fourth Social Lab workshop was designed to guide participants through a set of exercises that encourage reflection on environmental harms, responsibilities, and future possibilities within the European R&I ecosystems. Building on previous workshops, it aimed to engage with environmental and climate ethics within R&I with a special focus on the DNSH principle and collectively explore pathways toward more sustainable research practices. The workshop opened with a brief welcome and an introductory recap of the Social Lab process, situating participants within the broader trajectory of the project and outlining the goals for the one and a half days ahead.

First, participants engaged in a short interactive quiz or presentation to familiarize with the DNSH objectives and discuss common misconceptions. This was followed by an in-depth individual assessment, where each participant applied the DNSH framework to their own project using a structured evaluation sheet. This exercise laid the groundwork for a more critical dialogue on how harms are understood, assessed, and mitigated in practice.

Second, the workshop guided participants through a simulated ethics review process designed to encourage collaborative judgment and introduce questions and ideas that goes beyond the DNSH assessment from the previous exercise. The core element of this activity, an assessment sheet was built on the work done in WP3 on DNSH as well as the European Commission's forthcoming *Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research* (European Commission, 2025). In small groups, participants assumed the role of an Environmental Research Ethics Committee and used the previously mentioned assessment sheet to review anonymized project descriptions alongside their corresponding DNSH assessments. This approach allowed us to highlight differences

³ All workshops were conducted with informed consent of participants in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), using a consent form (Annex 4 – Workshop Consent Form) reviewed and approved by the German Reference Centre for Ethics in the Life Sciences. The Research Ethics Committee at UAB requested minor modifications to the Consent Form in accordance with current participatory research standards, resulting in the necessary ethics approval. The same was the case for AU who applied for ethics approval for SL4 at Aarhus University for the study RE4GREEN, Social Lab on Energy, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University, approval no. BSS-2024-098-L.

between individual and collective evaluations of the same projects, to probe and validate existing critiques of the DNSH principle, and to open space for exploring ethical considerations that the DNSH framework in its current shape does not fully capture.

A plenary discussion followed, where participants compared their own earlier self-assessments with the evaluations produced by their committees. This exchange highlighted the strengths and limitations of both individual and collective review processes and opened space for reflection on how evaluations of research projects take shape within R&I.

On the second day, participants reviewed summaries of a set of micromodules from WP4 designed to educate researchers and students on environmental and climate ethics topics in research. Through individual reflection and group discussion, they assessed their relevance from their own perspectives, explored learning pathways and discussed how these micromodules could be integrated into the current research ecosystem.

Finally, the workshop engaged participants in a worldbuilding exercise to think about a more sustainable research ecosystems and to explore the barrier and problems of getting there. Participants mapped existing harms and how they are currently being dealt with, envisioned new, more sustainable research landscapes in 2050, and identified barriers and strategies for change. These discussions encouraged participants to articulate the roles and responsibilities of different actors - including researchers, institutions, funders, policymakers, and indigenous communities amongst others - and to explore how and what systemic transformation might be desirable.

The workshop concluded with a collective reflection and closing round, inviting participants to share insights, identify remaining questions, and consider how the results and materials developed through the Social Labs and in the whole RE4GREEN project could support their ongoing work beyond the final in-person workshops.

3.1.1 The Do No Significant Harm Principle

The Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle forms a cornerstone of the European Union's Sustainable Finance Framework. It was formally established through the EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU) 2020/852, adopted in June 2020 and effective from 1 January 2022 for the climate-related objectives. The regulation provides a unified classification system for environmentally sustainable economic activities, ensuring that investments contributing to one environmental goal do not inadvertently harm others. Article 17 of the Regulation specifies that, to qualify as environmentally sustainable, an economic activity must *not cause significant harm* to any of the EU's six environmental objectives. It further outlines detailed criteria for assessing when an activity may be considered to significantly harm an environmental objective.

The six environmental objectives as defined in the Taxonomy Regulation (article 9) are as follows:

1. **Climate Change Mitigation:** Activities that reduce or prevent greenhouse gas emissions.
2. **Climate Change Adaptation:** Activities that reduce vulnerability to the impacts of climate change.

3. Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Resources: Activities that contribute to the preservation of water resources and marine ecosystems.
4. Transition to a Circular Economy: Activities promoting recycling, reuse, and resource efficiency.
5. Pollution Prevention and Control: Activities aimed at reducing environmental pollutants.
6. Protection and Restoration of Biodiversity and Ecosystems: Activities that conserve biodiversity and restore ecosystems.

DNSH played a central role in workshop 4 because it is a key reference point in the EU framework for avoid significant harms to the environment when it comes to funded activities. As part of the EU Taxonomy Regulation and the broader “do no harm” commitment under Horizon Europe, DNSH increasingly shapes how research projects are expected to account for their environmental effects. Focusing on DNSH allowed the workshop to anchor discussions in an existing regulatory framework that researchers and institutions are already expected to engage with in its current form.

At the same time, the DNSH framework received several critiques in the last years as explained in the forthcoming *Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research* (European Commission, 2025). It points out that DNSH was developed for economic and investment activities and does not translate easily to research and knowledge production, where impacts are often indirect, uncertain, and long-term. The notion of “significant harm” is difficult to define in research contexts, and current applications tend to privilege measurable indicators while overlooking broader environmental and ethical concerns. The guidance note (European Commission, 2025) also draws attention to structural constraints, such as existing research infrastructures and funding arrangements, which limit individual researchers’ room for change. These critiques contributed to frame Workshop 4 as a space to reflect critically on DNSH and to explore how it might be developed in ways that better fit the research ecosystem.

3.1.2 Micromodules

In close collaboration with WP4, this workshop also incorporated the emerging micromodules developed within the project. As the learning materials had reached a stage that allowed early engagement, participants were provided with concise summaries of the modules currently available. These summaries served as a basis for individual reflection and group discussion, enabling participants to assess the relevance, clarity, and potential usefulness of the materials in their own professional contexts. By inviting feedback at this stage, the workshop aimed not only to familiarize participants with the pedagogical direction of the micromodules but also to help shape their further development and final refinement. The session therefore functioned both as a testing ground of the content already prepared and as an opportunity to ensure that the evolving learning resources reflect the needs and expectations of those who may eventually use them.

3.1.3 Modifications of the international Social Labs

Social Lab 7 – University of Tokyo, Japan

Social Lab 7 coordinated by the UTokyo team focused on research ethics, environmental harm, and responsibility in the context of post-disaster rural revitalization in Iitate Village, Fukushima. Rather than approaching the research area from a macro-level, the lab worked from the specific conditions of a community still living with the long-term consequences of the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident. Through fieldwork and three smaller-scale workshops, participants explored how environmental harms are understood, how responsibilities are distributed, and how R&I interact with local realities.

The Japanese Social Lab followed the general RE4GREEN Social Lab approach, but several adaptations were made. Most notably, all workshops were held in person and in the local language. The UTokyo team considered face-to-face meetings in Japanese important because of the sensitivity of the Fukushima context and language barriers that would exist in English when addressing issues such as nuclear contamination, land use, and responsibility. These in-person workshops were organized within the project budget by relying on local venues and existing academic and civil society networks.

The three in-person workshops took place in:

- Workshop 1: January 2025
- Workshop 2: May 2025
- Workshop 3: October 2025

Some exercises from the original Social Lab design were adapted or not fully implemented when the Social Lab organizers found them difficult to apply to the Japanese context. Workshop 2 examined the relation to the EU Green Transition Goals in the rural, depopulated, and post-disaster area of Iitate village. Workshop 3 focused on the DNSH principle and on reflecting on environmental research ethics in general with the Iitate Village revitalization project in focus.

The findings from workshop 1 have been integrated into the first implementation report. Workshop 2 and 3 findings can be found in Section 5.

Social Lab 8 – University of Cape Town, South Africa

Social Lab 8 by the UCT team decided to hold workshop 2, 3 and 4 as a joint and larger in-person event designed with greater fit to the needs, concerns, and relevant interests of the South African context.

The workshop by the UCT team was held in July 2025 and was titled “Exploring the Ethics of Green Transition-focused Research and Innovation in Agrifood Systems.” The decision to focus on agrifood systems alone, instead of the four divergent themes explored in the first (online) workshop, was made because it became exceedingly difficult to recruit participants from the four themes (lab-grown meat, digital agriculture, payments for biodiversity conservation, and the bioeconomy) into the second workshop. A significant number of potential participants resisted recruitment as they did not see the value in participating in a workshop which was

intended to support European Union (EU) policy rather than South African policy. By recruiting participants from different sectors, but interested, invested, and active in a single area, namely agrifood, we were able to assure them that their voices would be relayed, not only to South African policy makers (three senior level government officials attended the workshop), but through RE4GREEN, to the EU. Further value for participants was that they could network with others interested in this subject within their respective fields.

The workshop consisted of short presentations to stimulate discussion and reflection, followed by room for questions of clarification and discussion. A series of participatory exercises which drew from RE4GREEN's examples, participants' own knowledge, the presentations, and the discussion and reflections, followed. The presentations included a short background to the RE4GREEN Project; a review of the green transition policy landscape; a summary of the synergies between the South African bioeconomy and G20 policy frameworks; a look at key research ethics and integrity issues; and a case study on digital innovation and agriculture.

A number of the participatory exercises were based on the templates for the European Social Lab Workshops 1, 2 and 3. These were:

- An introduction to ethics and integrity concerns raised in the RE4GREEN Social Labs thus far.
- Adding ethics and integrity concerns from an agrifood perspective as well as exploring possible solutions at multiple levels.
- A gallery walk, examining and questioning the skills, knowledge and attitudes needed for ethical agrifood research and innovation (R&I).

A fourth exercise was conceptualised to give participants the opportunity to express their vision of an ethical agricultural R&I system for green transitions in the Global South in a creative way. Groups of five worked together on this vision, using Lego pieces, found objects and other materials to construct an ethical R&I system for agrifood in the Global South.

The results of the international labs' workshops are summarized in section 5.

3.2 Participation in Workshop 4

Following the interviews and three online workshops, the Social Lab participants were invited to join the final step of the Social Lab process, the in-person workshops. To expand the coverage of the participation and account for individuals who could not join, we recruited additional participants. In total, we had 78 participants across the SLs. The gender distribution of participants included 43 females, 33 males, and 3 non-binary individuals.

Participation by sectors were research performing (54%), civil society and media (21%), public sector including funders and research ethics committees (9%), private sector (10%), and other (6%) (Figure 9).

Most participants were from Europe, with some joining from other regions as well. The geographic locations of the participants' organisations covered most of Central, Western,

Figure 9: Workshop 4 participation by sector.

Northern, and Southern Europe. International labs had participants from Japan (SL7) and South Africa (SL8). Besides that, some participants joined SLs from countries like Armenia, Kazakhstan, USA, Uganda, Zimbabwe, and Chile (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Geographical distribution of WS4 participants. Armenia: 1, Austria: 6, Belgium 2, Chile: 3, Croatia: 1, Denmark: 1, Finland: 2, Germany: 11, Greece: 1, Hungary: 1, Italy: 2, Japan: 3, Kazakhstan: 1, Luxemburg: 1, Netherlands: 4, Norway: 1, Portugal: 2, South Africa: 17, South Korea: 1, Spain: 9, Switzerland: 1, Uganda: 1, UK: 5, USA: 3, Zimbabwe: 1 (If the participants have double affiliations we counted all of them.)

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Participant familiarity with the DNSH principle

As the main theme of the workshop was the DNSH principle, a brief opening exercise was to get to a common ground with what the principle is, familiarize with the objectives and map how much participants are familiar with it. Due to the structure of the exercise there is no statistical data on the familiarity of the DNSH principle, but most of the participants were not or only partially familiar with the DNSH principle even though many of them have experience with EU-funded projects.

3.3.2 Participant self-assessments of significant harms

Before the workshop we asked participants to bring a research project of their own that they know well and can use as part of this exercise. Each participant got an assessment sheet (see Annex 3) where they had to evaluate the project against each of the DNSH principles. Below are the results of this exercise.

Climate Change Mitigation

Common findings across all Social Labs

Across the Social Labs, participants most often explained potential harm to climate change mitigation because of energy use, transport, and material lifecycles. Even when projects did not directly emit greenhouse gases, many participants reflected on indirect impacts such as energy-intensive digital processes, international travel, or the use and production of special equipment, alongside of natural resources. A recurring theme across labs was uncertainty about how far along the value chain they were expected to assess the impacts. Several participants noted that lifecycle emissions of technologies were unknown or difficult to access, and that “significance” remained vague. It became clear that harms to mitigation were not always straightforward to identify and often depended on interpretation of project boundaries.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants often identified travel-related emissions as significant contributors to potential harm, including field trips, international project travel, and construction logistics. Several projects also raised concerns about emissions related to new technologies such as 3D batteries and solar installations, particularly where manufacturing processes were unknown or energy intensive. Similar issues appeared in *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, where energy demands from AI training, semiconductor production, and hardware usage were viewed as potential harms to mitigation. In *SL4 (energy)*, participants described how energy-intensive upscaling phases or utilisation of research outputs might conflict with mitigation objectives. Projects in *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)* pointed to emissions arising from agricultural trials, including N₂O release, as well as from producing technological equipment. In *SL1 (health, culture & civil security)*, harms ranged from disposal of non-biodegradable materials to minor but cumulative energy use.

Climate Change Adaptation

Common findings across all Social Labs

Most participants viewed their projects as neutral or positive about adaptation, with only isolated cases of identified harm. Many projects aimed to strengthen resilience through ecological restoration, improved planning, or better monitoring systems which participants interpreted as inherently supporting adaptation. Where harms appeared, they tended to reflect issues of unequal access to technologies, systemic barriers, or vulnerabilities created by the design of research projects. Across labs, a common uncertainty involved distinguishing between harm to adaptation and harm arising from climate impacts on the project itself.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants observed that high-tech agricultural solutions could reduce adaptive capacity if they remain accessible only to a minority of farmers. They also noted tensions where adaptation-oriented interventions, such as indoor farming or alternative cultivation systems, might undermine mitigation or introduce new vulnerabilities. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants highlighted how participatory processes could inadvertently steer municipalities toward choices that weaken existing adaptation strategies, such as relaxing traffic restrictions or increasing heating use. *SL4 (energy)* offered a related concern regarding projects involving large-scale water extraction, where adaptation impacts were uncertain. In the other labs, projects largely appeared adaptation-neutral or supportive, and no significant harms were described.

Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Resources

Common findings across all Social Labs

Participants found water-related harms harder to assess than other DNSH dimensions, especially when their projects had no direct interaction with water bodies. Common concerns included indirect water consumption embedded in technological production, risks arising from chemical use or industrial processes, and uncertainty about thresholds for what constitutes unsustainable water use. Projects involving ecological restoration or pollution monitoring were often considered as contributing positively to this objective.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)*, participants identified harms tied to industrial and extraction activities, such as lithium extraction, the use of fossil groundwater, and heavy-metal recycling processes, all of which risked aquifer depletion and contamination. *SL2 (digital, industry and space)* raised concerns about water-intensive semiconductor manufacturing and the trade-offs between high water consumption during production and gains during later use. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants pointed to pressures created indirectly by rising energy demand such as increased water use linked to battery production or data-centre infrastructure. *SL4 (energy)* reported smaller-scale concerns relating to water over-extraction and use, also emphasizing that this objective does not properly address the impacts caused by water overuse. Other labs' participants described their work as largely neutral or beneficial to water systems.

Transition to a Circular Economy

Common findings across all Social Labs

Participants generally struggled to clearly determine their projects' relationship to circular-economy principles. Many projects produced little physical waste, but participants recognised that their use of equipment, consumables, and digital infrastructures as resource demands. A recurring cross-lab concern was the absence of clear indicators in the DNSH framework: without guidance on what counts as circular, participants sometimes defaulted to everyday examples such as printing, single-use event materials, or outdated hardware.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants highlighted that many materials used in biological sampling, laboratory work, and field measurement are difficult to recycle, and that chemical pollutants and plastics often persist beyond the project lifecycle. Some noted that circularity gains may require high-tech solutions that themselves lack circular design. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants pointed to the limited recyclability of new technologies such as 3D batteries and to short-term waste created during transitions to renewable energy. In *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, concerns centred on hardware obsolescence and organisational replacement policies. *SL4 (energy)* had explored uncertainties around lifecycle comparisons and whether project outputs genuinely supported circularity. In other labs, circular economy issues were mentioned only briefly.

Pollution Prevention and Control

Common findings across all Social Labs

The most common pollution related concerns involved emissions from travel, construction, energy use, and material production. Projects aiming to reduce pollution in society (e.g., monitoring or policy-support projects) tended to assess themselves as low-harm, but participants still recognised indirect pollution from their own activities. Several labs expressed difficulty judging pollution impacts when these were diffuse or embedded in upstream production processes rather than occurring within the project itself.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants identified pollution risks related to high energy use, increased waste, dust and air pollution from travel to research sites, and the mobilisation of existing pollutants during agricultural trials. Projects in *SL3 (climate and mobility)* described small-scale pollution from construction and uncertainties about pollutant release associated with new battery technologies. In *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, harms included chemical pollution linked to industrial processes, concerns about space-debris, and emissions from transporting people and materials. *SL4 (energy)* noted uncertainties about long-term environmental effects tied to material choices, while *SL1 (health, culture & civil society)* raised issues related to manufacturing pollution and inadequate transport alternatives.

Protection and Restoration of Biodiversity and Ecosystems

Common findings across all Social Labs

Participants generally identified few direct harms to biodiversity and ecosystems, with many projects described as either neutral or beneficial, especially those involving ecological

monitoring, restoration, or resilience planning. However, participants across labs struggled with uncertainty about long-term or indirect ecological effects, and several noted that without clear indicators or a defined scope, their assessments risked being overly narrow.

Social-lab-specific findings

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, biodiversity harms were linked to land-use change, the removal of small habitats during field experiments, and tensions between biodiversity protection and agricultural practice. Participants also discussed how new conservation measures might run into stakeholder resistance, creating additional risks for ecosystems. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, projects involving new battery technologies raised concerns due to the absence of compensatory ecological measures or restoration strategies. In *SL4 (energy)*, some participants mentioned lifecycle-related biodiversity risks. *SL2 (digital, industry and space)* reported limited harms, mainly associated with resource extraction for semiconductor materials, and *SL1 (health, culture & civil security)* referenced potential ecological impacts arising indirectly from manufacturing contexts.

Discussion of self-assessment results

Understandability of DNSH objectives

Most participants across the labs stated that the objectives were too broad, insufficiently explained, or difficult to apply in practice to their own projects. Several participants explicitly noted that assessing harms requires clarity about the scope: whether the evaluation should focus on the research process, the project's direct outputs, or the long-term consequences of research outputs and technologies developed. Furthermore, participants working on socio-cultural or desk-based research questioned whether their work should undergo the same assessment as technology-focused projects, as they found it "impossible to anticipate material consequences." Others highlighted that following causal chains too far leads to the conclusion that "you will always find some emission somewhere", so assessing their significance is key.

A recurring concern in several labs was the lack of thresholds or clear definition for "significant." Without guidance, some participants interpreted "significant harm" very narrowly and concluded their project produced no harm, while others adopted a more expansive reading and concluded that *any* technological activity - such as using energy, hardware, human and natural resources or materials - might violate the principle. In *SL2 (digital, industry & space)*, participants pointed out that some objectives were "not always applicable" to digital or data-driven projects, while others struggled with objectives that seemed "too broadly described." In *SL4 (energy)*, participants noted missing indicators, overlaps between objectives, and a need for clearer boundaries between harm categories. In *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)*, participants repeatedly struggled with whether DNSH should be applied deontologically (no harm allowed) or whether consequentialist reasoning (balancing harms and benefits) was permissible, indicating that the conceptual framing itself created uncertainty. Overall, objectives were understood at a surface level, but participants often lacked the conceptual and methodological tools to assess them meaningfully and apply them clearly to their own (research) project.

Were there harms related to environmental objectives that the assessment did not cover?

Individuals across labs consistently identified gaps in the DNSH framework, noting harms that were relevant to their projects but not captured by the six DNSH objectives. A widespread concern across labs was the absence of socio-environmental harms, including community well-

being, human health, labour conditions, inequality, and impacts on vulnerable groups. Participants argued that the environmental harms in DNSH cannot be fully separated from social harms, especially when environmental degradation disproportionately affects certain populations. The question whether the environmental assessment of a project should be separate from ethical and social impact assessment was a central topic.

Many participants also pointed out missing environmental categories. Land use appeared repeatedly as an overlooked harm, particularly in *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, where land consumption, soil preservation, and landscape changes were central to their research. Some labs noted that invasive species, pollination dynamics, and ecological interactions should be explicitly mentioned and assessed rather than implicitly assumed. Harms from noise, dust, and local-level pollution were seen as underrepresented, especially in labs where construction or fieldwork takes place. Participants also raised the issue of harms caused by inaction or delay, such as when climate-positive technologies paradoxically allow existing harmful systems to persist longer, for example, “clean coal” technologies.

In some labs, participants mentioned harms unique to their fields that DNSH does not address. For example, space debris, harm related to AI and data use, resource depletion through semiconductor manufacturing, or greenwashing. Others emphasised dual-use harms, meaning that research that appears harmless within a project may have harmful applications once implemented elsewhere. Finally, many noted the absence of harm quantification methods, making it impossible to assess the magnitude or intensity of harms, even if the type of harm was identifiable.

Did people feel they were the right person to be conducting the self-assessments? Did they indicate whether others should be involved and whom?

Responses varied across Social Labs and participants. Many felt they were at least *partially* the right person because they understood their project’s aims, methods, and context better than anyone else. This included coordinators, researchers deeply involved in day-to-day implementation of projects, and participants with environmental or sustainability expertise. Some also viewed the exercise as beneficial because it forced them to reflect critically on their work, even when they did not feel like they have the right knowledge to do such an assessment.

However, many people raised uncertainty or lack of expertise around such an assessment.

Reasons included:

- lack of disciplinary expertise (e.g., chemists lacking ecological knowledge, social scientists lacking training in environmental impact assessment);
- fear of being biased, particularly when evaluating their own work individually;
- lack of authority or oversight over certain aspects such as industrial partners or supply chains;
- inability to assess long-term or indirect harms, such as AI resource use or downstream technological impacts;
- feeling “too deep in the technical research” to take an objective perspective;
- or simply having no knowledge in environmental impact assessment in their usual work.

Across all labs, there was strong agreement that a single individual should not conduct DNSH assessments alone.

Participants suggested and encouraged to involve multiple experts and/or stakeholders with different backgrounds in an assessment like this.

Common suggestions and opinions:

- bring together environmental scientists, LCA specialists, social scientists, engineers, IT specialists, and domain experts;
- project beneficiaries, affected communities, and local authorities, especially where decisions have social or ecological implications;
- independent experts or environmental and social safeguard specialists to counteract bias;
- ethics committees, regulatory bodies, or institutional sustainability offices;
- material scientists, circular-economy experts, pollution and waste specialists for highly technical assessments;
- and, in some cases, funding agencies or political bodies, especially for large-scale or highly consequential projects.

Several labs emphasised that assessments should be ongoing, not one-time, and that projects should receive structured guidance, training, or a shared “common language” to conduct DNSH assessments consistently.

3.3.3 Ethics Committee Role-Play Assessment

In this exercise participants were asked to form Environmental Ethics Assessment Committees. The rationale behind this exercise was to mimic a real-life committee, practice collective judgement and also to explore the assessment of harms through different questions than assessing against the objectives from the DNSH principle. The exercise has been created through integrating the work of WP3 on DNSH as well as the *Guidance Note on Assessing and Managing Risks of Environmental Harm in EU-Funded Research by the European Commission* (European Commission, 2025). It aimed at validating or critiquing the work on the two aforementioned documents. Below are the findings of the exercise structured along categories of responses.

Interpreting harm

Similarly to the self-assessment participants across labs raised the fact of how difficult it was to determine whether harms had been properly identified or adequately prevented. In many cases, harms were mentioned only in broad terms or not at all, leaving committees unsure whether these omissions reflected an absence of harm or an absence of analysis. The meaning of “significant harm” in particular, generated repeated debate, especially in *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, where participants questioned whether significance should be judged in absolute terms, in comparison to alternatives, or through a balance of harms and benefits. Committees often concluded that they could not tell whether harm was prevented because they lacked insight into project methods, life-cycle effects, or downstream consequences. Even when harm seemed minor or unlikely, participants noted that the lack of mitigation planning raised doubts about whether prevention had truly been considered.

Mitigation and compensation of harms

Where committees identified harms or risks, they frequently highlighted that mitigation strategies were often missing or incomplete. Some projects simply acknowledged a potential issue but did not explain how it would be addressed; others implied mitigation but offered no detail about feasibility or responsibility. Several committees observed that even when harms could not be prevented, compensation or restorative measures were not described.

Participants in *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)* argued that expecting individual projects to compensate for systemic harm is unrealistic, and that responsibility must be shared across institutions and sectors. In *SL4 (energy)*, some participants emphasised that even seemingly small harms should be recognised and accompanied by practical steps to reduce them. Across labs, there was a shared sense that mitigation and compensation require clearer thinking than most project descriptions demonstrated.

Balancing harms and benefits

In many labs committees had substantial conversations on the balance between expected benefits and potential harms, but they varied in how confidently they felt able to assess it. Project descriptions often mentioned environmental or social benefits in broader terms, but these were rarely linked back to the harms identified, making the comparison difficult. Some participants, especially in *SL4 (energy)*, argued that assessing benefits requires consideration of what would happen if the project were not carried out, or whether alternative approaches might produce more favourable outcomes. Others noted that benefits tend to appear only after a project's completion, which complicates efforts to judge them alongside immediate impacts. Despite these challenges, committees generally agreed that balancing harms and benefits is an essential part of such a review process, but clearer guidance, more information, different expertise are needed.

Accounting for affected communities, ecosystems, and more-than-human interests

Committees frequently raised concerns about whether projects had adequately considered those most likely to be affected, including ecosystems, Indigenous or local communities, and marginalised populations. In several assessments, committees noted that people living in vulnerable situations were only briefly mentioned, without meaningful discussion of participation or consent. *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)* highlighted confusion in interpreting "harm to other species". Amongst many labs, participants found that while harms to ecosystems were sometimes recognised, they were often not explored deeply. In general, any assessment around harm to other species was lacking. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)* some participants mentioned ecosystems or local environments, but no specific non-human species were discussed.

Future Generations

Most committees indicated that projects made at least some reference to long-term effects or future generations, but these were rather indirect or implied than explicitly analysed. Participants noted that future-oriented impacts, like long-term resilience, adaptation benefits, or intergenerational justice were occasionally explained. In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants raised the challenge of how far into the future an assessment should extend and how to distinguish short-term project impacts from long-term consequences, especially if we consider post-project impacts. The discussions showed that while the idea of

future generations was not completely ignored, but the DNSH objectives are not incentivizing these reflections and clearer expectations would be a valuable addition to an assessment.

The question of responsibility and scope: the limits of individual projects

In many Social Labs, participants questioned what can be expected of a single project when harms often stretch beyond its direct impacts and general scope. Many argued that projects should acknowledge and be aware of harms that seem to be more systemic and beyond their control. As a common theme participants explained that single projects cannot be held responsible for solving all issues they touch upon. *SL2 (digital, industry and space)* members strongly expressed that certain harms, especially those arising from industrial systems, global supply chains, or policy choices lie beyond what a project team can meaningfully manage or mitigate. In *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)* participants stressed the need for broader institutional, governmental, or industry collaboration when harms intersect with systemic issues such as water depletion or waste management. At the same time, several groups agreed that even small projects can model good practice by being transparent about limitations, anticipating harm where possible, and engaging in partial solutions.

Expertise, bias, and the value of collective ethical decision making

Participants stressed the importance that such an environmental ethics assessment benefits from multiple perspectives and that no single person is likely to have the expertise needed to judge all relevant harms. This was particularly evident in *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, where reviewers found themselves evaluating unfamiliar technologies and noted how easily lack of expertise can make judgment more difficult. Similar challenges were mentioned in *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, where participants struggled to evaluate harms outside their agricultural knowledge. Many also reflected on biases inherent in self-assessments and found the external, committee-style exercise was valuable because it revealed blind spots in their original reasoning.

The results of this exercise showed us the importance of multidisciplinary committees, open discussions, and iterative review processes that engage with questions of harms.

Link to the Guidance Note of the European Commission

This exercise above highlighted many issues and validated important critiques on the DNSH framework.

Across the Social Labs, participants' experiences strongly underpin the critique already articulated in the European Commission's Guidance Note (European Commission, 2025) that the DNSH principle, as derived from the Taxonomy Regulation, is difficult to transfer from economic and investment contexts to research and knowledge production. The Guidance Note explicitly acknowledges that DNSH was perceived by stakeholders as ill-suited to research activities and insufficiently supportive of "honest reflection about eventual negative environmental impacts". This critique was empirically confirmed in the workshops, where even experienced researchers (who also work in EC-funded projects) struggled to interpret the six DNSH objectives in relation to their own projects. In particular, participants found the objectives overly broad, conceptually abstract, and lacking methodological guidance, resulting in highly divergent interpretations of what counts as "significant" harm. The Social Labs thus

reinforce the Guidance Note's argument that DNSH requires contextualisation, interpretation, and more practical support if it is to function as more than a formal compliance requirement.

Another critique in the Guidance Note concerns the limits of project-level responsibility and the presence of structural constraints such as existing infrastructures, path dependencies, funding arrangements, and industrial partnerships. Participants across the Social Labs not only echoed this concern but added important nuance by showing how these constraints shape researchers' everyday ethical reasoning and choices. While the Guidance Note recognises that individual researchers cannot resolve systemic harms, workshop discussions revealed how this ambiguity creates uncertainty about accountability: participants were unsure whether DNSH assessments should extend to supply chains, downstream technological applications, or long-term societal effects. The Social Labs add empirical depth to this critique by illustrating how researchers oscillate between overly narrow assessments (to remain within perceived responsibility) and overly expansive ones (leading to the conclusion that all research inevitably violates DNSH). This highlights a practical tension that the Guidance Note identifies, namely, how to acknowledge systemic harms without paralysing project-level ethical judgement.

The workshops also strongly support and extend the Guidance Note's critique of narrowly framed environmental assessment. The Guidance document explicitly embeds environmental harm within broader research ethics principles, including justice, respect for communities, and intergenerational equity, and argues that environmental impacts cannot be separated from social and ethical consequences. Participants across the Social Labs independently arrived at this conclusion, repeatedly pointing out that DNSH fails to capture socio-environmental harms such as impacts on community wellbeing, inequality, labour conditions, land use, and vulnerable groups. An additional insight from the Social Labs is the emphasis on harms caused by inaction or delay, for example when research enables incremental improvements that prolong environmentally damaging systems. This perspective complements the Guidance Note's ethical framing by showing how researchers themselves perceive DNSH as insufficiently attentive to dynamic and relational forms of harm.

Finally, both the Guidance Note and the Social Labs converge on a critique of individualised self-assessment and the risk of disciplinary blind spots. The Guidance Note explicitly warns that applicants and researchers may lack the expertise needed to identify environmental harms and encourages collective, multidisciplinary assessment. The Social Labs provide concrete evidence of this problem: participants consistently expressed discomfort with assessing harms outside their disciplinary knowledge and recognised biases when evaluating their own projects. The ethics committee role-play exercise added further insight by demonstrating how collective deliberation exposes overlooked harms, weak mitigation strategies, and unexamined assumptions. In this sense, the Social Labs go beyond confirming the Guidance Note's recommendations by showing how collective ethical assessment not only improves accuracy but also changes how researchers understand responsibility, uncertainty, and environmental ethics in practice.

3.3.4 Review of relevance of micromodules

Across all labs participants expressed strong overall support for the micromodules. All groups indicated they would use them, mainly because they address topics that are increasingly

relevant but insufficiently integrated into everyday research practice, ethics review, and training. The micromodules were seen as appropriate, practical, and aligned with currently emerging needs in R&I regarding environmental ethics. The feedback provided on the summaries of micromodules, their relevance and the suggested training pathways will be directly streamlined to WP4. Below is a general summary of key points from the micromodule session in the workshops.

Accessibility, framing, and language

Several labs noted that some modules rely on academic or STS-oriented language that may exclude non-academic stakeholders or practitioners. Participants emphasized that it would make the micromodules more accessible if the social science jargon would be reduced and key concepts would always be clarified. Furthermore, they advised that moving from concrete, real-life examples toward theory is often more helpful rather than the other way around. Also, adapting examples to the background of specific discipline and audience would also contribute to more success of the micromodules.

Where the micromodules could be used

Participants consistently described the micromodules as useful tools for researchers across different stages of the research process. They were seen as particularly valuable during project design and proposal development, where they can help integrate sustainability and ethical considerations from the outset rather than as an afterthought. Researchers also highlighted their relevance for fieldwork and laboratory preparation, as well as for ongoing reflection by PhD candidates, early-career researchers, and interdisciplinary research teams.

At the institutional level, the micromodules were viewed as having significant potential as training and capacity-building resources. Participants suggested their use in ethics committees, research management, postgraduate education, and lifelong learning programmes. They were also seen as suitable for integration into university curricula, micro-credential schemes, online courses, and possibly certification or accreditation systems related to sustainable research practices. Several labs emphasised that the greatest value would come from combining individual use by researchers with structural embedding at the institutional level, rather than treating the modules as optional or isolated learning tools.

They were also considered useful in ethics review and governance contexts, especially for raising awareness of environmental and climate ethics issues in the research context. While not all modules were seen as directly applicable to formal ethics assessment, participants noted their value in establishing a shared baseline of understanding among reviewers and decisionmakers.

3.3.5 Results of world-building exercise

The worldbuilding exercise generated the richest output for the workshop and engaged people to think on a systemic level when it comes to the R&I ecosystem and the environmental harms within.

In the six European Social Labs participants mapped out environmental harms and explored how they are currently being addressed (if they are being addressed at all) and then used those reflections as the starting point for imagining the future of a research ecosystem in 2050

that is more sustainable. Although each lab worked with different thematic areas there's been a lot of similarities in what structural and systemic problems they see in the research ecosystem as such: fragmented and unclear responsibility, weak governance, enforcement and supervision, deeply ingrained economic structures that do not promote sustainability, mindsets that resist change, and the view that going towards a more sustainable research ecosystem demands not only technical advances, policies, guidelines and tangible solutions but a shift (even a paradigm change) in how much and in what ways society values nature, knowledge, and a future that is inclusive and just not only for the people but for the planet as well.

Below is a written summary of R&I ecosystem maps that have been mapped out in-person on boards and sticky notes considering the environmental harms from the first exercise of the workshop.

How environmental harms are being addressed today and by whom

Across all the Social Labs, participants described a fragmented and complex landscape in which environmental harms in R&I are being addressed. Actions working on making the R&I ecosystem more sustainably today spreads across multiple levels and includes regulatory frameworks, environmental objectives, institutional guidelines, project-level practices, and individual responsibility. Participants found that despite this rich landscape, harms are being addressed through overlapping and often poorly coordinated actions by a wide range of actors, with substantial gaps in enforcement, supervision, accountability, and systemic integration.

Central role of policymakers, regulators, and funders

Participants across several Social Labs identified policymakers, regulators, and public authorities as key actors bearing a huge responsibility for addressing environmental harms, primarily through regulation, standards, and strategic objectives and frameworks. These include environmental laws, climate targets, policies and guidelines intended to shape research, industrial activity, and innovation practices. In several cases, participants emphasized that such frameworks exist but are inconsistently applied, weakly enforced, or poorly aligned across local, national, EU and international levels.

For example, in SL3 (*climate and mobility*), participants described national governments, municipalities, and the EU as defining objectives and guidelines related to transport emissions and pollution prevention, with cities expected to translate these into concrete mobility policies. In SL4 (*energy*), policymakers were also described as major players in regulations and for setting requirements, for example for private companies to consult affected communities before decisions are made.

Funding bodies were also often depicted as influential actors, particularly through the design of funding calls, eligibility criteria, and reporting requirements. In SL5 (*fresh waters and oceans*), participants noted that funders sometimes impose specific conditions or monitoring requirements aimed at mitigating environmental harm, yet these measures were seen as insufficient to ensure long-term sustainability or systemic change beyond individual projects

Across labs, participants emphasized that while policy and funding frameworks exist, they are often weakly enforced or poorly coordinated across different governance levels.

Researchers and research institutions: responsibility at the project level

Amongst many Social Labs researchers and research-performing organizations were described as addressing environmental harms primarily at the level of individual projects and everyday practices. This includes research design choices (e.g. avoiding harmful methods where possible) efforts to reduce travel-related emissions, basic waste management in laboratories, choosing sustainable materials, minimizing pollution and raising awareness of energy and water use linked to digital infrastructures and so on. However, participants consistently emphasized that such actions are largely voluntary and constrained by existing institutional incentives and resource limitations.

In *SL4 (energy)*, participants noted that small-scale toxic waste is being handled differently based on different cultural approaches through local institutional practices, rather than through a standardized, international system. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants explained that researchers tend to reflect on their environmental impact on the project level and sometimes make individual choices to have meetings online or use a more sustainable way of transport, while digital energy use is barely being addressed.

In several labs, participants highlighted that researchers are often expected to accept the existence of environmental harms that are systemically ingrained by funding systems, infrastructure choices, or industrial supply chains.

Actors in industry and private sector: partial engagement and resistance

Industry players, technology developers, and infrastructure providers, were often described to have an ambivalent role. In some cases, companies contribute to harm reduction through innovations (that benefit the planet), recycling practices, improving efficiency, promoting sustainability culture. In other cases, participants highlighted resistance to regulation, limited concern for environmental impacts (e.g. water consumption of computational infrastructure), the prioritization of short-term economic interests over environmental considerations or greenwashing.

For instance, in *SL1 (health, culture, and inclusive society)* and *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, participants discussed how companies respond to regulatory pressure and funding incentives but at the same time lobby against stricter environmental rules do not contribute to meaningful change. In *SL4 (energy)*, participants explicitly noted that cloud providers, supercomputer developers, and IT service providers currently do not seem to care much about the environmental impacts of computational infrastructure, like water consumption and land use.

Similarly, in *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, companies were described as engaging in innovation and competition related to addressing certain environmental harms, but at the same time they are afraid of major changes as they might cause consumer complaints.

The role of civil society, communities, and citizens

Civil society organizations, NGOs, different communities, and citizens were widely recognized as important actors in raising awareness, advocating for environmental protection, and

participating in decision-making processes. However, their role was often described as advisory or reactive rather than decisional.

In several discussions, like in *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)* participants explained that responsibility for harm mitigation is implicitly being shifted onto individuals, through lifestyle changes, consumer choices, or “responsible behaviour”. Whilst participants viewed these as necessary, they also thought they are insufficient in the absence of stronger systemic and institutional measures, and a different mindset in how we view nature.

In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, participants highlighted citizen assemblies and community participation as mechanisms through which local knowledge informs project design and policy proposals, particularly where livelihoods or mobility systems are affected.

In *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)*, participants emphasized long-term engagement with communities to address participation fatigue and conflicts between cultural, environmental, and research priorities, while noting that such engagement is rarely sustained beyond project funding periods.

Overall patterns

Through mapping today’s R&I ecosystem participants’ experiences suggest that environmental harms are being addressed through very widely spread and non-synchronized actions, rather than through a coherent systemic approach. While many actors are working on mitigating harms or contributing to more sustainable practices in some shape or form, responsibilities are often diffuse, enforcement mechanisms are weak, and long-term impacts are insufficiently monitored and supervised. Participants repeatedly explained that existing efforts tend to focus on compliance and mitigation at the surface level, rather than addressing deeper structural drivers of environmental harm embedded in research priorities, funding models, and economic incentives.

Reimagined research ecosystems in 2050

In their future imaginaries participants across labs tended to move beyond incremental improvements to the current system. Instead, they described an R&I ecosystem in 2050 that would address today’s environmental harms through a deeper systemic change, clearer responsibilities, and a change in mindsets and underlying values and hence every-day practices. In these imagined futures, sustainability was often no longer viewed as a separate criterion to fulfil compliance, but as a defining and guiding paradigm shaping governance, research, and everyday decision-making.

In Figure 11 we can see an example of how participants mapped out the research ecosystem of 2050.

Reimagined roles of policy makers and public authorities

By 2050, policymakers were envisioned as moving beyond reactive regulation toward proactive, long-term stewardship of planetary health. Participants across labs emphasized the need for policies that internalize environmental externalities, align incentives with sustainability goals, and prioritize long-term societal well-being over short-term economic growth.

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants imagined governments using taxation, subsidies, and public investment to actively support climate adaptation, biodiversity protection, and circular economy practices, while discouraging harmful production and consumption patterns. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, cities and national governments were envisioned as key actors in reshaping mobility systems, land use, and infrastructure to eliminate high-emission practices altogether rather than merely mitigating them.

Several labs also proposed compulsory impact assessments of policies and funding programs on future generations, positioning governments as explicitly accountable to long-term environmental outcomes.

Transformation of research and funding systems

Participants consistently argued that by 2050, environmental harms could only be effectively addressed if research systems and funding models themselves would be transformed. Rather than placing responsibility on individual researchers, future systems were imagined as embedding environmental considerations into evaluation criteria, funding structures, and institutional cultures.

In *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, participants proposed abandoning “publish-or-perish” logics in favour of assessment systems that reward quality, societal impact, and environmental responsibility. In *SL4 (energy)*, participants envisioned mandatory environmental work packages, long-term funding horizons, and standardized impact assessments as integral components of all research projects, ensuring that harms are anticipated and managed throughout the research lifecycle.

Across labs, funders were imagined as powerful agents of change, capable of enabling systemic transformation by prioritizing long-term, interdisciplinary, and community-engaged research rather than short-term, project-based outputs.

Stricter measures on industry players and clear accountability

In 2050, participants envisioned industry actors as operating within clearly bounded environmental limits, rather than voluntarily adopting sustainability measures. Across labs, companies were expected to be held accountable through stricter regulation, taxation of harmful activities, and transparency requirements.

In *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants proposed environmental taxes, extended producer responsibility, and value-chain accountability to ensure that industries internalize the environmental costs of production. In *SL2 (digital, industry and space)*, participants imagined transparent government–industry relations and the curbing of excessive corporate influence on policymaking, addressing power asymmetries that currently undermine environmental protection.

Technology developers, in particular, were imagined having to shift from technological solutionism towards viewing technologies as enablers for societal change.

Central role for communities, citizens, and mindset change

A recurring theme across all Social Labs was the conviction that environmental harms in 2050 could only be addressed through deep cultural transformation and active societal participation. Participants imagined citizens, communities, and civil society not as peripheral stakeholders but as central actors in co-creating sustainable solutions.

In *SL5 (fresh waters and oceans)*, participants emphasized long-term, trust-based partnerships with local communities, moving beyond extractive participation models towards shared governance and co-ownership of research outcomes. In *SL3 (climate and mobility)*, indigenous and local communities were envisioned as leading voices about land and water resources, with their knowledge recognized as essential to sustainability governance.

Education was repeatedly identified as a foundational lever for change, with several labs envisioning sustainability values embedded in formal education systems and lifelong learning, enabling individuals to meaningfully engage with responsibility regarding nature and acquire knowledge about environmental protection.

Addressing systemic drivers of harm

Finally, participants across labs converged on the view that by 2050, environmental harms could only be meaningfully addressed by engaging with systemic drivers such as growth-oriented economic paradigms, power concentration, and shared responsibility.

In *SL2 (digital, industry and space)* and *SL6 (food, bioeconomy & agriculture)*, participants explicitly questioned the compatibility of constant economic growth with environmental sustainability, imagining post-growth or degrowth-oriented systems in which success is measured through well-being, equity, and ecological integrity rather than GDP. Across multiple labs, participants emphasized the need to reconnect responsibility with decision-making power, ensuring that those who cause or benefit from harm are also accountable for preventing and repairing it.

Overall patterns

In participants' imaginary futures, environmental harms and systemic problems present today could be better addressed by 2050 through integrated governance, transformed research and funding systems, accountable industry practices, empowered communities, and cultural mindset change. Responsibility shifts from fragmented, individual-level mitigation toward coordinated, multi-level stewardship of planetary health, supported by enforceable rules and shared societal values.

3.4 Discussion of workshop 4 results

The DNSH self-assessment and the ethics committee role-play each revealed important findings about assessing, understanding and mitigating harms in research practices.

The self-assessment placed researchers in a position where they had to map their own projects onto a fixed set of environmental objectives, guiding them to explore and explain harms in

relation to pre-defined environmental categories. As a shared reflection across the Social Labs was that the DNSH does help to orient people's thinking, but it is rather difficult to assess against such broad categories, unclear thresholds or a clear and context-specific definition on "significant" harm. Furthermore, there was a lot of uncertainty about project boundaries, how far one should assess the impacts and what agency and responsibility a project has in relation to contributing to systemic harms. Participants also recognised the limits of individual judgment and highlighted the need for multi-disciplinary expertise and ongoing rather than one-off assessment. They also called for clearer guidance on how the DNSH objectives relate to broader social, ethical, and systemic harms, and where project responsibilities lie.

The worldbuilding exercise was designed for participants to reflect on environmental harms in R&I not only as individual problems, but as being part of the whole R&I ecosystem and its functioning. Across the six Social Labs, participants described a research ecosystem where responsibilities for addressing environmental harms are spread across many actors and institutional levels, but it is not synchronized, coherent and continuous. Although many policies, guidelines, funding requirements, impact assessments, bottom-up initiatives and individual practices already exist, participants highly criticized weak enforcement, unclear accountability, resistance in changing mindset and a lack of a shared future. This suggests that environmental harms are not sufficiently addressed not because they are unknown or ignored, but because existing measures are fragmented.

A recurring theme in the discussions was the gap between formal responsibility and practical action. Policy makers, regulators, and funders were widely seen as having a central role in shaping the R&I ecosystem through laws, standards, and funding frameworks. At the same time, participants emphasized that these frameworks are often inconsistently applied across governance levels and tend to focus on compliance rather than meaningful change. As a result, responsibility for mitigating environmental harms is frequently shifted onto researchers and research institutions, who mainly act at the project level but find it difficult to fight systemic structures that often underlie environmental harms. Many participants shared the view that researchers by themselves may try to reduce harms through everyday choices, efforts like these remain mainly voluntary and constrained by existing structures like funding models, given infrastructures or supply chains that they cannot easily influence.

When imagining the research ecosystem in 2050, participants eventually articulated a more crucial societal transformation. Sustainability should not only be a quality and evaluation criteria or reporting requirement, but a core value system in our mindsets that guides governance, research priorities, and evaluation systems. Such a new system would create stronger and more enforceable governance frameworks, initiate clearer accountability for industry actors, and transform research and funding systems. These changes in the R&I ecosystem were identified as necessary to address environmental harms more effectively. Importantly, participants emphasized that such changes would require aligning incentives with long-term environmental and societal goals, rather than continuing to reward short-term wins (for the environment) or economic growth alone.

Communities, civil society, and citizens were envisioned as playing a more central role in shaping research agendas and decision-making processes, with greater recognition of local and indigenous knowledge. Education and long-term engagement were seen as key to

supporting this shift, enabling people to better understand their relationship with nature and their responsibility toward future generations. Overall, the discussions point to a shared understanding that meaningful change by 2050 would depend on coordinated action across actors and levels, combined with a broader societal shift in how research, innovation, and environmental responsibility are understood.

4 International Social Lab Results

4.1 Social Lab 7 - University of Tokyo, Japan, litate Village

The UTokyo lab decided to focus on recovery and resilience at the site of litate Village, heavily impacted by the 2011 Fukushima nuclear accident. To adapt to the unique case and Japanese cultural conditions, UTokyo deemed it most appropriate to hold a series of smaller in-person workshops with Social Lab participants, rather than multiple online and one longer in-person workshop. UTokyo Lab participants have highlighted the critical need to balance economic incentives and technological advancements with environmental sustainability. Justice and equity were underscored as fundamental aspects of ethical considerations, with particular concern about marginalized communities and their vulnerability to environmental harm. The issue of gender dimensions in environmental ethics was discussed as an area that requires further exploration in policy frameworks in Japan.

Workshop 2: Green Transition Goals and Rural Realities (May 2025)

Workshop 2 examined the relation to the EU Green Transition Goals in the rural, depopulated, and post-disaster area of litate village. Participants broadly agreed that the goals felt poorly aligned with litate's situation and were based on assumptions drawn from urban or metropolitan contexts. Through collective discussion and mapping exercises, participants identified several locally relevant issues. These included land-use pressure from large-scale solar developments, gaps in digital connectivity, declining rural mobility, debates around forest decontamination, and limited local influence over decisions made at national or corporate levels.

An actor mapping exercise was used to explore who is responsible for addressing these issues and over what time horizons. While this exercise followed the intended Social Lab design, participants questioned whether standard actor categories were sufficient. Some suggested that long-term responsibility cannot be captured without considering entities such as nature or future generations. The exercise also highlighted tensions between local knowledge and top-down governance, reinforcing concerns raised in the first workshop.

Workshop 3: DNSH and Environmental Research Ethics in Japan (October 2025)

Workshop 3 focused on the DNSH principle and on reflecting on environmental research ethics in general. The discussion focused mostly on examining the litate Village revitalization project directly through the assessments.

Participants raised strong critiques of DNSH, arguing that it does not adequately address structural and historical harms, uneven power relations, or questions of community autonomy. While some DNSH categories, such as biodiversity or pollution, were seen as relevant, participants questioned the meaning of “significant harm” and who has the authority to define it. The simulated ethics review further showed that existing assessment frameworks struggle to address intergenerational responsibility, cultural loss, and long-term environmental uncertainty in post-disaster settings.

The conversations emphasized the need to expand research ethics in Japan beyond a narrow focus on the protection of humans. Participants argued that ethics frameworks should more clearly address environmental harm, long-term responsibility, and impacts on local ecosystems and future generations. Ethics review was seen as a potential space for open discussion about justice and responsibility, rather than a purely procedural requirement.

A key theme was the importance of community involvement, especially in regions affected by long-term environmental damage such as Fukushima. Participants stressed that ethics processes should require meaningful engagement with local communities and include mixed ethics committees with academics, officials, residents, NGOs, and practitioners. Responsibility was understood as an ongoing, responsive practice, where researchers remain present, share knowledge openly, and adapt projects based on community feedback, while also valuing lived, tacit, and indigenous forms of knowledge.

Participants questioned whether terms such as “reconstruction” fully capture what is needed, proposing alternatives like “revitalization” or “newborn” to emphasize social, cultural, and ecological renewal. Overall, the lab called for a shift from passive ethics focused on avoiding harm to more proactive ethics aimed at supporting well-being and long-term care within R&I systems.

Link to the European Social Labs

From the Japanese SL perspective, especially in the context of Iitate Village, the findings closely align with the European labs’ critique of harm assessment frameworks. European participants noted that tools such as DNSH struggle to account for long-term, uncertain, and systemic harms, particularly those that extend across generations. These limitations were also central to discussions in Japan, where participants focused on the lasting environmental, social, and cultural consequences of the Fukushima disaster.

A key shared concern was uncertainty over who defines harm and on what basis. In the European labs, participants questioned how “significant harm” is judged and whose knowledge informs those judgements. Japanese participants raised similar questions, pointing out that standard assessment frameworks tend to assume stable governance and clear lines of responsibility. In post-disaster Fukushima, however, responsibility is dispersed across state institutions, private actors, and historical policy decisions, making project-level assessments insufficient.

Participants repeatedly pointed out that R&I activities in Iitate take place within wider systems shaped by national policy decisions, corporate interests, and long-term environmental risks that cannot be resolved through project-level assessments alone. As a result, existing harm

assessment approaches were seen as ill-suited to contexts where responsibility is distributed across multiple actors and where the causes of harm are structural rather than incidental.

4.1 Social Lab 8 - University of Cape Town, South Africa

Across the two-day workshop in July 2025 held by the UCT team, discussions consistently returned to questions of power, justice, and responsibility in R&I in general and particularly in agrifood systems. Participants questioned how research agendas are set, who benefits from research outcomes, and whose knowledge counts as legitimate. A recurring concern was that research ethics and integrity are too often treated as procedural or compliance-based, rather than as ongoing, relational practices that must respond to historical and contemporary injustices in the Global South.

Participants highlighted a persistent gap between research outcomes and real-world impact. While significant research is conducted in South Africa, many questioned how this knowledge translates into implementation, policy change, or tangible benefits for communities. Several contributions pointed to the lack of co-creation with farmers and other stakeholders, noting that research often prioritises publications and predefined indicators over societal needs. This concern was closely linked to critiques of “evidence-based policy,” where power asymmetries can allow corporate or external actors to dominate knowledge production and decision-making.

Discussions on bio-economy and digital agriculture further underscored these issues. Participants noted that dominant framings often separate economy and environment, a division traced to colonial histories and contested by small-scale farmers’ lived experience. In relation to digital innovation, concerns were raised about data extraction, weak enforcement of existing laws, and limited awareness among farmers of how their data are used. The need for free and prior informed consent, farmer co-development of technologies, and mechanisms such as data trusts was emphasised as central to ethical practice.

Trust, solidarity, and epistemic justice emerged as cross-cutting themes. Participants stressed that research relationships are shaped by power, funding, and historical trauma, and that ethics frameworks must explicitly acknowledge these realities. Several discussions emphasised discomfort as a productive space, arguing that ethical research requires engaging honestly with complicity, coloniality, and the emotional dimensions of research practice, rather than avoiding them.

Exercise 1:

The first exercise identified key environmental, climate, and integrity concerns in agrifood R&I. The issues receiving the highest number of votes were *justice and equity* and *how decisions are made*, followed by *competing needs and priorities*, *epistemic justice*, and *environmental impact*. These priorities were shared across sectors, indicating broad agreement that governance and decision-making processes are central ethical challenges, not secondary considerations

Participants also identified concerns that were missing from existing frameworks, including the need for context-sensitive measures of value, safe spaces for co-creation, accountability in

research partnerships, and a re-evaluation of what counts as legitimate knowledge. Additional points highlighted the neglect of health–agriculture linkages, the marginalisation of indigenous knowledge systems, multi-species justice, barriers to accessing research funding, and the disconnect between academia and the communities research claims to serve.

The reflection following this exercise led to the articulation of a shared “preamble,” calling for explicit recognition of historical harm, power imbalances, non-monetary forms of value, multiple worldviews, and the limits of good intentions. Ethics was framed as iterative and reciprocal, rather than a one-off assessment.

Exercise 2:

In the second exercise, participants mapped responses to identified concerns across different levels. At the individual level, integrity, transparency, reflexivity, and emotional awareness were emphasised. At institutional level, participants called for stronger guidance on international partnerships, mandatory responsible conduct of research training, and research processes that move beyond human-centred ethics to include environmental concerns.

At national and international levels, participants highlighted the need for clearer policy implementation, participatory and decentralised funding processes, budget equity, and greater scrutiny of public–private partnerships. A notable proposal was to “turn the research gaze” toward power structures in the Global North, rather than focusing solely on those affected by environmental harm.

Exercise 3:

The creative exercise produced four distinct but overlapping visions of an ethical agrifood R&I system. Across the sculptures, recurring elements included trust, equity, transparency, reflexivity, horizontality, and the integration of human and non-human concerns. Participants emphasised flexibility, ongoing learning, co-creation of research questions, and the need for research systems that are bounded yet adaptable across contexts.

The discussion following the exercise distilled key characteristics of an ideal system: research that is meaningful and accessible; attention to history and injustice; solidarity across projects and actors; decentring profit as the primary driver; and recognition of the interconnectedness of people and nature.

Exercise 4:

The final exercise assessed proposed competence profiles for researchers and innovators. Most competences were considered relevant, particularly those related to environmental and climate justice, stakeholder engagement, continuous learning, and respect for local and traditional knowledge. Participants critically engaged with the wording, often arguing that recognising injustice is insufficient without actively seeking redress.

Several competences were seen as ambiguous or incomplete, especially those related to “do no significant harm,” systems thinking, and alternative economic models. Participants stressed the need for flexibility, multi-stakeholder involvement, and clearer attention to whose visions,

futures, and values are being prioritised. Training was seen as necessary not only for researchers, but also for institutions and funders.

Overall, the discussions and exercises revealed strong convergence around the need for research ethics and integrity frameworks that are participatory, historically informed, and attentive to power. Rather than calling for entirely new principles, participants emphasised changing how ethics is practised: who defines it, how it is enacted, and whether it leads to meaningful change.

Link to the European Social Labs

From the perspective of the South African Social Lab, many of the concerns raised echo those discussed in the European workshops, particularly doubts about how well existing frameworks can capture real-world environmental harm. European participants questioned whether principles such as DNSH can meaningfully guide research practice when harms are indirect, cumulative, or shaped by broader social and political conditions. Similar concerns were raised in the South African lab, where participants stressed that environmental impacts cannot be separated from issues of justice, inequality, and power.

A shared concern across the South African and European findings is the tendency for responsibility to be placed on individual researchers, while wider institutional and funding structures remain largely unexamined. European WS4 discussions pointed to the risk that harm assessments become procedural exercises rather than spaces for reflection and learning. South African participants expressed comparable scepticism, noting that ethical requirements often fail to address how research agendas are shaped, whose priorities dominate decision-making, and how historical patterns of extractive research continue to influence present-day collaborations.

What is particularly important in the South African findings is the emphasis on history and context. Participants repeatedly argued that environmental ethics frameworks for research must acknowledge colonial legacies, past research harms, and ongoing global inequalities. From this perspective, initiatives such as RE4GREEN were welcomed as openings for dialogue but also approached with caution. Participants stressed that such initiatives will only be meaningful if they allow Global South perspectives to shape ethical standards in substantive ways, rather than treating them as supplementary or consultative inputs. Without changes at institutional and funding levels, there was concern that new frameworks risk reproducing the very power imbalances they seek to address.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

Over the course of more than 1,5 years (May 2024 – December 2025), the RE4GREEN Social Labs have engaged more than 170 researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders across eight labs to identify, validate, and deepen our understanding of climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues in R&I. By conducting 124 interviews, and four rounds of participatory workshops, we have mapped out the key ethical issues, systemic barriers, and potential strategies that could characterize the pursuit of a just and sustainable green transition. Additionally, we engaged with the DNSH principle and explored how environmental harms are

currently understood and addressed and collectively envisioned R&I ecosystems that are more sustainable in the long term. In this concluding section we summarize our findings.

The interviews uncovered a wide spectrum of climate and environmental ethics concerns connected to R&I. These issues, drawn from all eight Social Labs, reflect systemic tensions that cut across disciplinary, sectoral, and geographical lines.

In the first round of workshops, participants engaged in a collective exploration of the key issues identified during the interview phase, assessing their relevance and impact within their respective R&I contexts. Among the issues, *environmental impacts* - both from research activities and technological outputs - and *justice and equity* emerged as the most significant and widely shared concerns. Also considered highly relevant were the challenges of *resource intensity*, *technoeconomic constraints*, and *competing needs and priorities*, which often create tensions between innovation, sustainability, and social responsibility. While viewed as less prominent, issues such as the *gender dimension*, *resource use within research practices*, and the *impact of technologies on animals* were still acknowledged as important and deserving of further attention, especially within specific disciplinary or regional settings.

As part of the second round of workshops, we explored how stakeholders see themselves advancing or hindering green transition goals. In general, there was an overarching optimism and positive contribution highlighted, but this could well be due to the limited knowledge about the specifics of the green transition. In our further analysis we would like to link the explore issues and map their details to the green transition to get a clearer picture of the hindering aspect.

In the third round of workshops, participants reflected on the draft recommendations and the RE4GREEN competency framework, focusing on their relevance, clarity, and usefulness for research practice. Across the six Social Labs, there was broad support for the overall direction of the recommendations. Participants stressed, however, that environmental responsibility should not be framed as an issue for individual researchers or universities alone. Instead, they highlighted the need to strengthen institutional responsibility and to situate recommendations within existing processes and frameworks that already shape R&I. These discussions helped clarify where additional guidance, practical examples, and targeted institutional support would be most valuable, and they directly informed the final policy brief and the orientation of WP3.

Discussions in the third workshops also focused on capacity building and training needs. Participants generally considered the RE4GREEN competency framework to be relevant but emphasised that competencies are developed and applied in different contexts, ranging from general awareness to highly specific application cases. Training was seen as most effective when it is concrete, practice-oriented, and grounded in real-life examples. At the same time, participants pointed out that successful training depends on practical conditions, including sufficient time and resources, opportunities for interdisciplinary exchange, and space for discussion and reflection. These insights are shaping the development of training pathways and micromodules in WP4.

In the fourth round of workshops, participants engaged more directly with questions of environmental harm, responsibility, and systemic change through a DNSH self-assessment, an ethics committee role-play, and a worldbuilding exercise. The DNSH self-assessment helped

orient participants' thinking by asking them to map their own projects against a set of environmental objectives. While this structure supported reflection, many participants found it difficult to assess their projects against broad categories, unclear thresholds, and an ambiguous understanding of what constitutes "significant" harm. Uncertainty also emerged around project boundaries, how far impacts should be considered, and what responsibility individual projects have for contributing to wider systemic harms.

The worldbuilding exercise shifted attention from individual projects to the wider R&I ecosystem. Participants described a system in which responsibility for addressing environmental harms is spread across many actors and levels but remains poorly coordinated and fragmented. Although many policies, guidelines, and initiatives already exist, they were often seen as weakly enforced and lacking clear accountability. Participants highlighted a persistent gap between formal responsibility and practical action, with researchers frequently left to manage environmental concerns within tight structural constraints. When imagining the research ecosystem in 2050, participants articulated the need for a more fundamental shift in which sustainability becomes a guiding value for governance, research priorities, and evaluation systems, supported by stronger coordination across actors and greater involvement of communities and society at large.

Insights from the international Social Labs echo these concerns, showing that difficulties around defining harm, responsibility, and project boundaries are even more acute in contexts shaped by post-disaster recovery actions and global inequalities. Environmental and climate ethics in R&I and must be understood as context-dependent, historically informed and shaped by power relations, long-term impacts, and the lived realities of affected communities. The South African findings highlight that research ethics initiatives like RE4GREEN will only be meaningful if they substantively integrate Global South perspectives, address historical injustices and structural inequalities, rather than reproducing existing power imbalances through largely procedural or consultative approaches.

5.1 Challenges and coping factors

The scope of this project was shaped by ambitious objectives, aiming to engage a broad spectrum of participants from diverse countries, sectors, and stakeholder groups. This inclusive approach successfully ensured representation of a wide array of voices and perspectives. However, it is important to note that the resulting data should not be interpreted as statistically representative of the whole European Research Area. Due to the extensive diversity across categories such as career levels, stakeholder groups, countries, and disciplines, we were unable to conduct extensive, representative, comparative analyses across these dimensions. Instead, our findings are intended to identify areas warranting further exploration, validation, or discussion within the existing literature on environmental and climate issues in the context of research ethics and integrity. The findings also point out opportunities to creatively address climate and environmental ethics issues in R&I, and provide an insight into the level of awareness, generally, of these issues among researchers and other R&I stakeholders.

Recruitment posed a number of challenges, primarily due to budget constraints that limited us primarily to online workshops. While this format enabled broader geographic participation, it often proved less engaging than in-person workshops, where participants tend to be more

immersed and interactive. Based on participant feedback indicating that the online sessions were overly long and mentally demanding (even at only 4 hours with 1.5 hours of lunch/break time built in), we have decided to shorten the third online workshop to a total duration of two hours.

The project requires a significant time commitment from participants – three online workshops and one in-person session – which is contributing to a higher rejection rate than initially anticipated. In the original use of Social Labs in the *NewHoRRizon* project, budget was available to conduct 3 in person 1.5-day workshops per 18 labs. Despite being more time intensive, the quality of in-person experience, opportunity to network and exchange in person, to delve more deeply at length into topics, may offer a recruitment edge to consider for future social-lab-based research. In the interim, to address this issue, in addition to reducing the time request in Workshop 3, we have made considerable efforts to recruit replacement participants whenever original invitees were unable to attend.

An additional challenge emerged from the involvement of international Social Labs based in South Africa and Japan. These labs operate within very different contexts compared to their European counterparts, particularly in relation to the European Green Deal. As a result, we had to adapt our methodology to accommodate these differences while remaining aligned with the overall goals of the project.

The design of our workshops was uniquely tailored to the goals of the RE4GREEN project. As such, some exercises yielded mixed results. One key learning was the importance of more intensive facilitation during breakout or group sessions, particularly to ensure accurate notetaking in a standardized manner across labs. Additionally, we found that providing even more detailed instructions and concrete examples would help participants better understand and engage with the exercises. Higher level of detail also helps better assure consistent facilitation across the labs.

A final point relates to our planned inclusion of citizen scientists. Initially, we intended to involve two citizen scientists per SL. However, due to unresolved issues with the European Commission regarding their compensation, Citizen Scientists were not included in the interviews and the first two workshops. Although in the second implementation phase all SLs made efforts to recruit citizen scientists, participation remained limited. Uncertainties around the compensation of citizen scientists remained in this second phase as well and once resolved it contributed to delays and difficulties in recruitment. Furthermore, many potential participants did not identify as citizen scientists or were unfamiliar with the term, and those who were active often worked in narrow fields, such as biodiversity monitoring, which often did not align with the thematic focus of SLs. As a result, full representation of citizen scientists as originally envisaged was not achieved. A limited number of citizen scientists did participate in the final workshops. Their perspectives were incorporated into the overall findings of the SL workshops.

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7 References

Csábi, A., Nishi, M., & Bernstein, M. (2025). Social Lab Implementation Report 1: environmental and climate ethics issues in the context of R&I and for the green transition. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682897>

European Commission (2025). Guidance Note on Assessing and Managing Risks of Environmental Harm in EU-Funded Research, 2025.

Annex 1: RE4GREEN Social Labs Workshop 3: Review and Respond to the RE4GREEN Competence Profile

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RE4GREEN COMP

The knowledge, skills, and attitudes supporting environmentally aware research and innovation

Executive summary

Achieving a just green transition in Europe, as envisaged in the European Green Deal, requires training across the research and innovation sectors on how to adequately consider environmental, climate and broader justice considerations in research and innovation activities. Competence profiles can help ensure all actors have the skills, knowledge, attitudes and abilities to contribute to the green transition.

The RE4GREEN Competence Profile is based on extensive interviews and surveys with environmental education and research integrity specialists. Its structure emulates the EU GreenComp framework, which defines sustainability as “prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries” (Bianchi et al 2022).

RE4GREEN Comp will be used as a basis for designing ‘micromodules’ that can be combined into tailored training pathways for students, researchers, ethics reviewers, and citizen scientists.

How you can help: Instructions for participants

1. **Review the Competence Profile.** Carefully read through the competence profile provided on the following pages.
2. **Identify Relevant Competences.** Determine which competences are *most relevant* and *most needed* in your specific field of expertise. Make a note of your selections.
3. **Provide Practical Examples.** Reflect on your research or industry specialism. Identify and describe practical examples or case studies that illustrate how the competences you’ve chosen are applied (or not).
4. **Assess Training and Educational Needs.** Consider how training for these competences is currently being supported, facilitated, and delivered. Note the formats in which this

training occurs (e.g., workshops, online courses, mentoring, etc.). Highlight any educational needs or skills gaps you observe in relation to these or other competences.

1. Embodying Sustainability Values

1.1 Valuing sustainability

Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice in the context of research and innovation.

Researchers and innovators should... reflect on how personal values and perspectives regarding the environment influence decisions and actions taken during the research process.

Researchers and innovators should... consider reducing environmental harms and increasing environmental benefits to be a professional responsibility in research and innovation.

Researchers and innovators should... apply the do no (significant) harm principle and precautionary principle in relation to research and innovation.

1.2 Supporting fairness

Researchers and innovators should... recognize the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice.

Researchers and innovators should... consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.

Researchers and innovators should... support equity and justice for present and future generations in research and innovation proposals.

Researchers and innovators should... conduct all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice in the green transition.

1.3 Promoting nature

Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.

Researchers and innovators should... perceive the needs and rights of other (non-human) species and of nature itself as a fundamental aspect of research ethics.

Researchers and innovators should... practice care and respect towards the environment and other species when designing a research or innovation project.

Researchers and innovators should... devise evidence-based strategies for improving ecosystem health as part of research and innovation.

2. Embracing Complexity

2.1 Systems thinking

Researchers and innovators should... define sustainability in research and innovation as a 'wicked problem' with multiple interdependent factors.

Researchers and innovators should... be aware that the complexity of environmental, climate and sustainability challenges can be emotionally impactful.

Researchers and innovators should... recognize the influence of time, space and context on the sustainability of research and innovation activities.

Researchers and innovators should... use systems thinking to determine the environmental consequences (including unintended consequences) of research and innovation activities.

2.2 Critical thinking

Researchers and innovators should... recognize potential trade-offs between competing priorities (people, planet, profit) in research and innovation.

Researchers and innovators should... evaluate the validity of information sources regarding environmental problems and potential solutions (e.g. technological solutions).

Researchers and innovators should... align project aims with alternative approaches towards growth and consumption which are informed by more sustainable and just economic models.

Researchers and innovators should... build in opportunities for critical reflection throughout research and innovation projects to ensure continuous alignment with sustainability principles.

2.3 Problem framing

Researchers and innovators should... identify common challenges, risks, and uncertainties related to the environmental and climate impacts of research and innovation activities in your field.

Researchers and innovators should... map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems.

Researchers and innovators should... openly and transparently communicate potential benefits and risks of a project to the environment, climate, and affected communities.

Researchers and innovators should... engage multiple stakeholders from the outset and incorporate their perspectives and priorities on environmental issues.

3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures

3.1 Futures literacy

Researchers and innovators should... envision sustainable outcomes and identify possible actions, innovations, and/or policies that would support these outcomes.

Researchers and innovators should... anticipate ethical concerns of emerging technologies and their environmental and climate impacts.

Researchers and innovators should... employ techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project.

Researchers and innovators should... align immediate research and innovation efforts with long-term sustainability visions, adaptively balancing present needs and long-term sustainability objectives.

3.2 Adaptability

Researchers and innovators should... consider emerging evidence on environmental harms caused by research and innovation, including the cumulative harms of all research and innovation activities.

Researchers and innovators should... monitor progress toward envisioned futures and adjust strategies based on new insights or changing circumstances.

Researchers and innovators should... mitigate against the environmental impact of research and innovation by considering alternate approaches (e.g., frugal innovation).

Researchers and innovators should... participate in continuous learning activities to ensure professional skills are applicable to changing ecological and social circumstances.

3.3 Exploratory thinking

Researchers and innovators should... understand how alternative disciplinary and role-specific perspectives can complement one another.

Researchers and innovators should... respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.

Researchers and innovators should... engage with key ethical debates regarding the environmental and climate impacts of a research and innovation project.

Researchers and innovators should... plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design).

4. Acting for sustainability

4.1 Political action

Researchers and innovators should... recognise that sustainable approaches to research and innovation exist within the context of wider political systems.

Researchers and innovators should... identify research and innovation priorities which can contribute to a just transition towards a sustainable society.

Researchers and innovators should... be aware of the access to knowledge, networks and platforms that your role entails, and use this to promote environmentally and socially responsible action.

Researchers and innovators should... strategically engage in policy dialogue and participatory processes for green initiatives as part of the research methodology or innovation cycle, when appropriate.

4.2 Collective action

Researchers and innovators should... remember the importance of teamwork and collective action in tackling environmental (including climate) issues.

Researchers and innovators should... demonstrate a capacity for accessible and collaborative work, for example through open science and FAIR data practices.

Researchers and innovators should... participate in environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field.

Researchers and innovators should... collaborate with multiple actors (such as policy makers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation.

4.3 Individual Initiative

Researchers and innovators should... recognise that everyone has a role to play in fostering sustainable approaches to research and innovation.

Researchers and innovators should... appreciate how personal research goals can contribute to global sustainability objectives, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Researchers and innovators should... be accountable for the environmental and social impacts of professional activities and take corrective actions where needed.

Researchers and innovators should... act as a green role model for other researchers and collaborators by applying sustainability competences in all areas of research and innovation including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.

References

Bianchi, G., Pisiotis, U. and Cabrera Giraldez, M., GreenComp The European sustainability competence framework, Punie, Y. and Bacigalupo, M. editor(s), EUR 30955 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-46485-3, doi:10.2760/13286, JRC128040.

Annex 2: Total up-votes and down-votes of competences across all Social Labs.

Number	Competence group (#); competence sub-group (#.#); competence item (#.#.#)	Total up-votes	Total down-votes
1	Embodying Sustainability Values		
1.1	Valuing sustainability		
1.1.1	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice in the context of research and innovation.	14	2
1.1.2	Researchers and innovators should... reflect on how personal values and perspectives regarding the environment influence decisions and actions taken during the research process.	10	2
1.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... consider reducing environmental harms and increasing environmental benefits to be a professional responsibility in research and innovation.	20	2
1.1.4	Researchers and innovators should... apply the do no (significant) harm principle and precautionary principle in relation to research and innovation.	15	1
1.2	Supporting fairness	0	0
1.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognize the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice.	8	5
1.2.2	Researchers and innovators should... consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.	13	4
1.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... support equity and justice for present and future generations in research and innovation proposals.	14	1
1.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... conduct all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice in the green transition.	14	2
1.3.0	Promoting nature	0	0
1.3.1.0	Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.	13	4

1.3.2.0	Researchers and innovators should...perceive the needs and rights of other (non - human) species and of nature itself as a fundamental aspect of research ethics.	6	3
1.3.3.0	Researchers and innovators should... practice care and respect towards the environment and other species when designing a research or innovation project.	9	2
1.3.4.0	Researchers and innovators should... devise evidence - based strategies for improving ecosystem health as part of research and innovation.	7	3
2	Embracing Complexity		
2.1	Systems thinking		
2.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... define sustainability in research and innovation as a 'wicked problem' with multiple interdependent factors.	11	2
2.2.2	Researchers and innovators should... be aware that the complexity of environmental, climate and sustainability challenges can be emotionally impactful.	6	1
2.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... recognize the influence of time, space and context on the sustainability of research and innovation activities.	6	1
2.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... use systems thinking to determine the environmental consequences (including unintended consequences) of research and innovation activities	10	0
2.2	Critical thinking		
2.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognize potential trade- offs between competing priorities (people, planet, profit) in research and innovation.	14	3
2.2.2	Researchers and innovators should... evaluate the validity of information sources regarding environmental problems and potential solutions (e.g. technological solutions).	8	1
2.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... align project aims with alternative approaches towards growth and consumption which are informed by more sustainable and just economic models.	7	1
2.2.4	Researchers and innovators should ... build in opportunities for critical reflection throughout research and innovation projects to ensure continuous alignment with sustainability principles.	4	1
2.3	Problem framing		

2.3.1	Researchers and innovators should... identify common challenges, risks, and uncertainties related to the environmental and climate impacts of research and innovation activities in your field.	9	2
2.3.2	Researchers and innovators should... map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems.	11	3
2.3.3	Researchers and innovators should... openly and transparently communicate potential benefits and risks of a project to the environment, climate, and affected communities.	9	0
2.3.4	Researchers and innovators should... engage multiple stakeholders from the outset and incorporate their perspectives and priorities on environmental issues.	10	1
3	Envisioning Sustainable Futures		
3.1	Futures literacy		
3.1.1	Researchers and innovators should... envision sustainable outcomes and identify possible actions, innovations, and/or policies that would support these outcomes.	8	2
3.1.2	Researchers and innovators should... anticipate ethical concerns of emerging technologies and their environmental and climate impacts.	8	3
3.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... employ techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project.	6	5
3.1.4	Researchers and innovators should... align immediate research and innovation efforts with long-term sustainability visions, adaptively balancing present needs and long-term sustainability objectives.	9	1
3.2	Adaptability	0	0
3.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... consider emerging evidence on environmental harms caused by research and innovation, including the cumulative harms of all research and innovation activities.	6	3
3.2.2	Researchers and innovators should... monitor progress toward envisioned futures and adjust strategies based on new insights or changing circumstances.	8	2

3.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... mitigate against the environmental impact of research and innovation by considering alternate approaches (e.g., frugal innovation).	4	3
3.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... participate in continuous learning activities to ensure professional skills are applicable to changing ecological and social circumstances.	9	2
3.3	Exploratory thinking	0	0
3.3.1	Researchers and innovators should... understand how alternative disciplinary and role specific perspectives can complement one another.	6	0
3.3.2	Researchers and innovators should... respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.	14	5
3.3.3	Researchers and innovators should... engage with key ethical debates regarding the environmental and climate impacts of a research and innovation project.	7	0
3.3.4	Researchers and innovators should... plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design.)	6	7
4	Acting for sustainability		
4.1	Political action		
4.1.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognise that sustainable approaches to research and innovation exist within the context of wider political systems.	9	1
4.1.2	Researchers and innovators should... identify research and innovation priorities which can contribute to a just transition towards a sustainable society.	5	2
4.1.3	Researchers and innovators should... be aware of the access to knowledge, networks and platforms that your role entails, and use this to promote environmentally and socially responsible action.	11	0
4.1.4	Researchers and innovators should... strategically engage in policy dialogue and participatory processes for green initiatives as part of the research methodology or innovation cycle, when appropriate .	8	1
4.2	Collective action		

4.2.1	Researchers and innovators should... remember the importance of teamwork and collective action in tackling environmental (including climate) issues.	7	0
4.2.2	Researchers and innovators should... demonstrate a capacity for accessible and collaborative work, for example through open science and FAIR data practices.	8	0
4.2.3	Researchers and innovators should... participate in environmental and climate - positive initiatives within your research field.	6	1
4.2.4	Researchers and innovators should... collaborate with multiple actors (such as policymakers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation.	11	0
4.3	Individual Initiative		
4.3.1	Researchers and innovators should... recognise that everyone has a role to play in fostering sustainable approaches to research and innovation.	6	2
4.3.2	Researchers and innovators should... appreciate how personal research goals can contribute to global sustainability objectives, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG.s)	7	0
4.3.3	Researchers and innovators should... be accountable for the environmental and social impact of professional activities and take corrective actions where needed.	7	1
4.3.4	Researchers and innovators should... act as a green role model for other researchers and collaborators by applying sustainability competences in all areas of research and innovation including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.	6	1

Annex 3: Do No Significant Harm Self-Assessment Sheet

This assessment sheet is designed to evaluate whether a project causes harm to any of the ‘Do No Significant Harm’ (DNSH) criteria. Both the environmental impact of the activity itself and the environmental impact of the products and services provided by that activity throughout their life cycle (production, use, and end of life) must be considered.

Field of research:

Type of stakeholder:

Project:

Brief explanation of the project and key outputs:

Does the project harm...	Assessment (Yes/No/Partial)	Comments / Supporting evidence
Climate change mitigation, where that activity leads to significant greenhouse gas emissions.		
Climate change adaptation, where that activity leads to an increased adverse impact of the current climate and the expected future climate, on the activity itself or on people, nature or assets.		
The sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, where that activity is detrimental: (i) to the good status or the good ecological potential of bodies of water, including surface water and groundwater; or (ii) to the good environmental status of marine waters.		
The circular economy, including waste prevention and recycling, where: (i) that activity leads to significant inefficiencies in the use of materials or in the direct or indirect use of natural resources such as non-renewable energy		

<p>sources, raw materials, water and land at one or more stages of the life cycle of products, including in terms of durability, reparability, upgradability, reusability or recyclability of products;</p> <p>(ii) that activity leads to a significant increase in the generation, incineration or disposal of waste, with the exception of the incineration of non-recyclable hazardous waste; or</p> <p>(iii) the long-term disposal of waste may cause significant and long-term harm to the environment.</p>		
<p>Pollution prevention and control, where that activity leads to a significant increase in the emissions of pollutants into air, water or land, as compared with the situation before the activity started.</p>		
<p>The protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, where that activity is:</p> <p>(i) significantly detrimental to the good condition and resilience of ecosystems; or</p> <p>(ii) detrimental to the conservation status of habitats and species, including those of Union interest.</p>		

Final reflection questions:

- Are the harms you are asked to assess understandable?
- Are there harms related to environmental objectives that the assessment does not cover?
- Do you feel you are the right person to be doing this kind of assessment? Why or why not?
- Should others be involved in doing these kinds of assessments? If so, who?

Annex 4: Participant Information and Consent Form

Project title: Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition

Project acronym: RE4GREEN

European Commission Horizon Europe Grant Agreement no.: 101131706

Task 2.2 Social Lab Workshop Participant Information and Consent Form

Contact person for questions about RE4GREEN:

Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath

German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE)

Bonner Talweg 57

53113 Bonn

+49 228 738110

re4green@drze.de

Contact person for your Social Lab:

Introduction

You have been invited to participate in the RE4GREEN Social Labs. Before you can decide to participate in this study, you must understand its nature, significance, scope, as well as the risks and potential benefits. Please read the following information carefully. If you have any uncertainties, questions, or require further information, please contact us.

What is RE4GREEN?

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. **RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal.** RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up Social Lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

Aim of this research activity

We are inviting your participation in the RE4GREEN [Social Lab XXXX] to learn from your insights on climate and environmental ethics issues and relevant training needs in your area of research.

A "Social Laboratory," or Social Lab for short, is a group of people brought together to tackle complex social problems. Just as scientific and technical laboratories push the boundaries of human knowledge, Social Labs aim to push boundaries in addressing social issues. These labs explore complex issues, going beyond traditional laboratory boundaries to address matters like culture, values, politics, and the environment.

When applied to research and innovation (R&I) contexts, Social Labs provide a proven method for engaging diverse stakeholders over time to understand and address important societal issues. In the RE4GREEN project, Social Labs bring together experts from various fields to explore environmental and climate research ethics and integrity challenges, supporting efforts for a greener future.

Details about your participation

As a participant in the RE4GREEN Social Labs, you will be invited to participate in three online workshops and one in-person workshop. Your expertise and experience will help us develop a deeper understanding of:

- **Issues:** Climate and environmental ethics and research integrity challenges in your field
- **Responses:** Ways in which your field is working to or might respond to such challenges
- **Resources:** The kinds of trainings, guidelines, and otherwise) that you might need to respond to such challenges in your research or practice

The approximate timing and duration of each Social Lab workshop is as follows:

- Online, workshop 1, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, December 2024 or February 2025: Climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues and training needs
- Online workshop 2, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, March or early April 2025: Responses to climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues
- Online workshop 3, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, June 2025: Guidelines, recommendations, and trainings to support responses to climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues
- In-person workshop 1, approximately 1.5 days, travel and accommodation expenses covered, September or October 2025: Climate and environmental ethics and environmental risk assessments; responding to the European Commission's "Do No Significant Harm" principle.

Risks and benefits of participation

Your participation will allow you to network and interact with researchers from across Europe that have a variety of areas of expertise, sectoral experience, and backgrounds. In addition, you may benefit from specialized training materials, guidelines and recommendations produced by the RE4GREEN project that address the specific ethical and integrity challenges you may encounter in your work.

It is expected that there will be no physical or psychological risks for your participation in the Social Labs. However, the workshops may address sensitive topics related to experiences in research ethics and integrity. To reduce emotional discomfort, you are encouraged to avoid speaking of specific names, organizations, and individuals. Social Labs facilitators have received training in inclusive and sensitive facilitation techniques to ensure a supportive and respectful environment during the workshops.

Compensation

You will be reimbursed for any travel and accommodation costs incurred while participating in the in-person Social Lab. The German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE) at the University of Bonn will initiate this payment via bank transfer following the workshop.

Please note that no other compensation will be provided for your participation in the study.

Data collection

Your name, affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography, and contact details will be the only personal data we process as part of this activity and will not be shared publicly. These data will be destroyed five years after the completion of the reporting phase at the end of the project, no later than June 2032.

An important component is to systematically collect and analyse the expert knowledge of relevant stakeholders on climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues. For this purpose, we request to keep documentation of workshop activities and notes from facilitation, as well as pseudonymised quotations from participants during the workshop. Results will be used for our systematic and scientific analysis of results, and will be pseudonymised, aggregated, and reported in summary form. It will not be possible to trace your personal data to any findings.

If you explicitly provide your consent below, audio and/or video recordings may be made during the workshops. These recordings will be used solely to aid in the transcription of the workshops and will enable us to pseudonymise the information shared during the workshops. Pseudonymisation is when personal information gets replaced with fake names or codes to keep it private. If you do not provide your consent to record the workshop, the facilitators will take handwritten notes instead.

All Social Lab workshops are convened under [Chatham House Rule](#): “When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.”

The data gathered from the Social Lab workshops will be pseudonymised using a random unique identifier. Results will be used to advance the work of the project in developing ethics and research integrity guidelines, reports to the European Commission, academic and popular publications, blog posts and conference presentations.

If you wish to be identified as a participant, this is also in your rights (e.g., an acknowledgment at the end of the report). If you agree to be acknowledged for your contribution to the workshops, only your name and affiliation will be indicated at the end of the relevant public project report and publications. However, your data from workshop activities will still not be associated to any specific sections or quotations (unless you instruct otherwise).

Data processing

- The legal basis for data processing is your voluntary consent (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR and Article 9(2)(a) GDPR).
- The person responsible for data processing is Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath at the German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE) (+49 228 738110, re4green@drze.de)

Participation in the Social Lab is voluntarily. You may stop participating at any time you want, without giving any reason. Data that relates to you will be destroyed and will not be used for the purpose of the project.

You have the right to request information about your personal data processed by us and to have any incorrect data rectified or erased. Subject to the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation, you also have the right to request the restriction of the processing or the transfer of your personal data. In cases of suspected violation of the data protection provisions you can contact the Data Protection Authority (https://www.bfdi.bund.de/DE/Infothek/Anschriften_Links/anschriften_links-node.html).

You also have the right to withdraw your consent at any time, verbally or in writing, and to object to the processing of your data, without any disadvantage to you. If you withdraw your consent, no further data will be collected. You may also request the deletion of your data that has not been published. Please note that the withdrawal of consent will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal and that your data may need to be further processed to prove compliance with the guidelines of good research practice.

The University of Bonn will not make any decision based solely on automated data processing which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.

Storage of data

Your data will be handled securely at all times. We will store your personal data until five years after the end of the final reporting period to the European Commission. This means that any quotations and data will be deleted after the completion of the project plus reporting period and no later than June 2032.

Your personal data, including contact information, and any direct quotations will be stored on the individual secure servers of the University of Bonn and never transferred. Your Unique ID and name will be centrally coordinated within the Consortium to avoid duplication of contacts. Only your affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of reporting to the European Commission in sensitive deliverables (e.g., on stakeholder participation). Only the anonymized summary reports of the Social Lab workshops will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of research and analysis.

Whenever data is collected, stored, used, or shared, there are risks to confidentiality. These risks can't be completely avoided and increase as more data is connected. Social Lab facilitators will take every possible step, using the latest technology, to protect your privacy.

You have the right to request information from the University of Bonn about the personal data stored about you (including a free copy of the data). You may also request the correction of inaccurate data and, if necessary, the transfer of the data provided by you and the restriction of its processing. Please contact the University of Bonn for this information.

For concerns regarding data processing and compliance with data protection requirements, you can also contact the following data protection officers:

- a) The data protection officer of the University of Bonn: Dr. Jörg Hartmann (joerg.hartmann@uni-bonn.de)
- b) The data protection officer of the Austrian Institute of Technology (Social Lab coordinators): Michael Löffler (michael.loeffler@ait.ac.at)

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority. If you have concerns regarding the handling of your personal data, you can contact the following authorities:

State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information North Rhine-Westphalia
PO Box 20 04 44
40102 Düsseldorf
Telephone exchange: +4921138424 - 0

Incidental findings

Although not anticipated, any incidental findings related to violations of research ethics and integrity that may arise during the Social Labs workshops will be treated with care. The University of Bonn will guide participants to the appropriate institutional, regional, or national authorities responsible for monitoring research ethics and integrity. Additionally, any unexpected findings will be promptly reported to the RE4GREEN management team at the University of Bonn to ensure transparency and accountability in addressing these matters. Throughout this process, the anonymity and autonomy of participants will be strictly respected.

Insurance

Please note that there will be no insurance provided for your journey to the in-person Social Lab workshop or your stay at the study site.

Consent Form

I, the undersigned, confirm that I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the information sheet. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about my participation in the Social Labs. I am participating in this research voluntarily and I am free to end my participation at any time without negative consequences. I may refuse to answer any questions I do not wish to discuss. I understand that I will be asked to provide, as relevant, professional or personal views and that the record of my involvement in the research will be kept confidential and anonymized (unless otherwise instructed and permitted).

I understand that the results of workshop activities will be kept and irretrievably deleted five years after the relevant reports have been submitted, and no later than June 2032. I understand that the extracted data from this exercise (pseudonymised, unless otherwise requested) will be used as input to project reports (which will be submitted to the European Commission and made available publicly on the project website and in a public repository). The data may also be used for other related research outputs such as publications.

Under the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (art. 13 and 14), the consortium has an obligation to inform of the purpose of the collection, use, storage, and retention of the information I have provided. I understand that the project will only collect information that is relevant to its activities. Any personal information will be stored on the University of Bonn's secure, enterprise level, password-protected internal servers, as described above. Anonymized information, as described above, will be accessible to only those involved in the RE4GREEN project or in sensitive reporting documents to the European Commission. The project will not transfer my personal information to third parties outside the project.

I also have the right of access to my personal data, the right to obtain the rectification of my data. I further have the right to obtain the restriction of processing or the right to transmit my data to another controller under the specific terms of the General Data Protection Regulation. In addition, I have the right to object to the processing of my personal data. If I am of the opinion that my data is processed unlawfully, I have the right to file a complaint with a supervisory authority.

I understand that this research conforms to European Commission guidelines.

I am free to contact Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath, coordinator of the RE4GREEN project, about any queries relating to my data or the project itself. His e-mail address is re4green@drze.de and telephone number is +49 228 738110. I may also contact the data protection officer, XXX, and local lab leader, XXX.

Additional disclosure options:

- I wish to include the name of my organization in the list of organizations participating in RE4GREEN Social Labs.

Yes No

- I wish to include my name in the list of participants in RE4GREEN Social Labs.

Yes No

- I agree to record the workshop using a recording device.

Yes No

To receive further communication about the project:

- I agree to be included in the RE4GREEN stakeholder database in order to be contacted by project partners for future activities of the project. I accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to receive further communication by email related to activities of the RE4GREEN project and accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to my details being retained by RE4GREEN partners to be contacted for a future study on research ethics and integrity training.

Yes No

Name

Organisation

Date and place

Signature

